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Wireless Communication Using Higher Frequency Bands

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Executive Summary

There is an ever-increasing demand on wireless system capacity to fulfill the rapid increase of the mobile data transmission requirements. Relying on further improvement of the utilization efficiency of the very limited spectrum at lower frequency band cannot satisfy such capacity requirement. In recent years, the research and development of technologies exploiting higher frequency bands, e.g., millimeter wave (mmWave), tera-Hertz or light waves are becoming more active. Especially, the mmWave technologies are taken into account for commercial deployment of 5G systems around 2020. On the other hand, there are also a lot of research activities on visible light communications in the academia, resulting in a wide range of experimental results and prototyping.

FuTURE FORUM members have actively contributed to the research and development of new technologies exploiting the rich spectrum at higher frequency band.

For mmWave, as it has been identified as an indispensable spectrum resource for the 5G systems, recent research activities are more focused on resolving the issues related to the industrial adaptation of mmWave related technologies. Detailed activities are made from the following aspects, and we provide full details for each of them in this paper.

Spectrum analysis. There is a wide range of frequency resources at mmWave bands, some are suitable for wireless communications whereas others are not. On the other hand, some of these resources were already used for other purposes, e.g., satellite communications, military use, etc. It is important for the industry to identify and to harmonize the good candidate spectrum for the global deployment of future wireless communication systems. Recent progress with FuTURE FORUM and associated originations.

Deployment scenario. Radio propagation behaves differently in low frequency band and in high frequency band. This will impact the future deployment of the mmWave based communication systems. Several potential deployment scenarios are discussed in this paper. The discussion provides a brief description of each scenario and key challenges to be resolved for a better deployment and usage of the mmWave spectrum.

Channel characteristics. A large number of channel measurement campaigns were carried out by different organizations to obtain a deep understanding of the mmWave channel characteristics, in order to identify the potential issues and look for corresponding solutions. Whereas some measurement results are revealed in FuTURE FORUM's previous publications [1], latest measurements focus on more details of the mmWave radio propagation, e.g., the small-scale fading, the effect of human body blockage, spatial domain properties, consistency in frequency domain, etc. In addition, recent progress on channel modelling in 3GPP and ITU are summarized.

Impact to system design. Given the mmWave radio propagation properties, analysis is made on different potential deployment schemes, considering single RAT deployment based on high frequency, single RAT deployment based on low frequency, and a hybrid usage of high and low frequency bands.

Key technologies. Among many of the open issues and the corresponding technologies to resolve them, some sample technologies, e.g., high frequency beam management, hybrid (analog and digital) beamforming incorporated in a MIMO-OFDM system, are presented. The summary of the technologies is not meant to be exhaustive, but to lead to more discussions on resolving the practical issues in order to ensure an efficient and effective usage of mmWave in practice.

It is the first time to summarize the recent research activities in visible light communications in FuTURE FORUM. The following aspects are captured to provide a full picture of different aspects related to the research on this field.

Spectrum analysis. It provides a general description of the spectrum that can be exploited for visible light

communication.

Deployment scenario. Several potential deployment scenarios of visible light communications are identified, mainly based on the feasibility and convenience of access visible light resources.

Channel characteristics. Several models are summarized to characterize visible light communication channels with respect to impulse response, frequency response, path loss, delay spread and so on. Those are useful the theoretical analysis and numerical verification of associated technologies.

VLC devices. Typical VLC devices are introduced with respect to general properties. Based on that, it is analyzed the potential application scenario for different types of devices.

VLC key technologies. Several key technologies, with respect to modulation, coding, multiplexing, equalization schemes, as well as dimming control are introduced.

Based on the review and summary of recent research activities in mmWave and VLC technologies. We see a better understanding of the channel characteristics of higher frequency band. Based on that, the commercial deployment of mmWave is very promising. The next focus in this area shall be the solutions to realize a system level deployment, and to make wireless communications over mmWave more efficiently and more cost-effectively. The presentation of the recent progress of VLC related research is intended for more attentions from industry for the future consideration of potential deployment and commercialization.

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1. Introduction

Wireless communication networks are to be further improved to meet the ever-increasing demand of wireless packet data volume. Compared to the 4G era, the mobile data traffic is expected to increase 1,000 fold by the year of 2020 to meet the 5G requirements, and around 10,000 fold by the year for 2030 for beyond 5G. Solutions are to be considered in different aspects, e.g., densification of transmission points or the cell deployment, enhancement of the transmission efficiency or the spectrum utilization efficiency based on the existing carrier frequency bands, and possible exploitation of new spectrum resources. Recent advances of the wireless transmission technologies, e.g., small cells, MIMO, CoMP, inter-cell interference mitigation, improves the initialization efficiency of the lower frequency bands for 2G/3G/4G deployments. However, relying solely on those lower frequency bands, or even considering some additionally available lower frequency bands, e.g., 3.5GHz, 4.9GHz, still cannot achieve the very demanding 5G requirement. Therefore, exploiting the spectrum in higher frequency band, e.g., above 6GHz is a must. The research on millimeter wave (mmWave) has been carried out for a while. Now mmWave is considered as a necessary spectrum resource for 5G communication systems. In recent years, there was also very active research in academia on communications over visible light. Such research activities are believed to attract the interests from industry in the near future. In this paper, we review the recent research and industrial activities on both mmWave and visible light communications. For each of the topics, several aspects are discussed, e.g., spectrum analysis, possible deployment scenario, channel characteristics based on channel measurement, some analysis of the impact of specific channel properties on system design, sampled key technologies, and so on.

2. mmWave Communications

2.1 mmWave Spectrum Analysis

2.1.1 FuTURE FORUM's mmWave Spectrum Analysis

Last year, Future FORUM issued their 5G spectrum white paper. Based on the China strong market demand forecast and frequencies to be considered in WRC-19 AI 1.13 for IMT-2020, FuTURE FORUM has brought our view for mmWave spectrum to promote extensive study for global harmonization, R&D progress for different frequency bands and also frequency sharing with existing incumbent systems. Therefore, we proposed 3 different frequency bands for candidate mmWave frequencies for 5G and gave our view to the frequencies bands for these 3 bands and 28GHz band as well.

24.25-27.5: This frequency range is a good candidate for a tuning range solution together with the 28 GHz frequency band (26.5/27.5-29.5 GHz), and is consequently considered as a good choice of pioneer band for early deployment in China.

31.8-33.4 GHz: This frequency band may provide a tuning range solution with the 28 GHz frequency band. If so, the same advantages would be achieved as for 24.25 – 27.5 GHz. However, this frequency band does not provide the same bandwidth as 24.25 – 27.5 GHz, it is not immediately adjacent to the 28 GHz frequency band, but directly adjacent to the passive services below 31.8 GHz, and may consequently suffer from difficulties in implementation design. There may in addition be a need for a guard band above 31.8 GHz limiting the available bandwidth further. It should be more difficult for deployment in comparison with 24.25 – 27.5 GHz.

37-43.5 GHz: The momentum in this frequency range is good due to the development in the U.S. and a good bandwidth could be provided. It is noted that the entire range may not become available globally, due to incumbents in parts of the band. However, a tuning range approach may enable a global harmonization in the sense that parts of the band can become available everywhere.

28GHz band considered in U.S, Korea and Japan: it has strong momentum globally, thus providing an opportunity for early availability of an eco-system with good economy-of-scale and potential international harmonization

On June 8th, 2017, China MIIT issued another public consultation request on 5G system frequency planning over 24.75-27.5GHz, 37-42.5GHz (or other millimeter wave bands). They requested to list the frequency usage and future plan for these 2 bands and give view of the major technical issues for 5G deployment in these bands and also the coexistence study and frequency management proposal. FuTURE FORUM has responded our view and submit our proposal to MIIT for mmWave bands using for 5G.

2.1.2 Detailed Analysis of IMT-2020 Requirements

Terrestrial IMT-2020 systems, incorporating the use of new enabling technologies like massive MIMO, benefit from the large potentially available bandwidths for higher frequency range (above 6 GHz, especially between 24.25-86 GHz) which will provide higher data rates and lower latency.

The spectrum needs for higher frequency range is used to satisfy the future development requirement of IMT-2020. The maximum one of spectrum needs, obtained from different factors such as user experienced data rate, peak data rate, spectral efficiency, expected device density and so on, is regarded as the final needs of higher frequency range for eMBB of IMT 2020.

According to Rec. ITU-R M.2083, the spectral efficiency for eMBB is expected to be three times higher compared to IMT-Advanced. Because of the high propagation loss and penetration loss in higher frequency ranges, the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency may not be expected to reach 3 times.

In addition, usage scenarios, including the associated expected coverage area, deployment environments, and target applications introduce technical requirements and conditions on a radio system that can impact spectrum needs.

Table 2-1 Deployment scenario for high frequency

Deployment scenario	Indoor hotspot	Dense Urban Micro
Frequency range	24.25-86 GHz	24.25-43.5 GHz
ISD	20 m	—

Scenarios involving high frequency bands could be divided into indoor and outdoor hotspot, micro layers in dense urban. The micro and hotspot scenarios are used to fulfil the requirement of extremely high transmission rate in frequency range between 24.25-86 GHz. Among the frequencies of 24.25-86 GHz, the frequencies of 24.25-43.5 GHz are more suitable for micro scenario due to better propagation characteristics, and the frequencies of 45.5 86 GHz are more suitable for hotspot deployment scenario due to larger continuous bandwidth. The frequency of 24.25-43.5 GHz can also be reused in indoor hotspot, but co-channel interference would decrease the spectrum efficiency accordingly.

Based on the current usage and future plan in China, the potential high frequency bands are listed below.

Table 2-2: Deployment scenario for high frequency [1]

Bands	Services
25.5-27 GHz	EESS (in-band)
25.25-27.5 GHz	ISS
24.65-25.25/27-27.5 GHz	FSS
31.8-33.4 GHz	RNS
37.5-42.5 GHz	FSS

By for there are 3 operators in China, which can also affect the spectrum needs.

To obtain the accurate spectrum needs, one detailed calculations involving aspects such as link budget and system-level simulations can be done, with which key technical performance requirements (e.g., peak data rate, user experienced data rate and area traffic capacity) should be satisfied.

Through detailed calculations, total spectrum needs for the higher frequency range between 24.25GHz and 86GHz are about 14.8-19.7GHz, and Table 2-3 shows the spectrum needs for the higher frequency range.

Table 2-3: Spectrum needs for 24.25-86GHz

	Hotspot	Micro
Total spectrum needs for 24.25-86GHz	14.8-19.7GHz	
Spectrum needs for 24.25-43.5GHz	9-12GHz	5.8-7.7GHz
Spectrum needs for 45.5-86GHz		—

2.2 Deployment scenario

2.2.1 Non-standalone

Due to the limited coverage of high frequency, the non-standalone operation can be considered to apply in the outdoor scenarios, e.g, stadium (as shown in Figure 2-1), outdoor hot-spot areas (as shown in Figure 2-2). Major features of such scenarios include large outdoor area, high user density, large traffic demand, low user mobility. Several challenges are to be solved for the deployment of high frequency in such scenarios. Those are demand for dense connectivity, outdoor throughput, necessary coordination between outdoor micro-cells and macro-cells, interference management among micro-cells, high-frequency antenna pattern design and planning of micro-cells for outdoor.

Figure 2-1: Outdoor stadium scenario

Figure 2-2: Outdoor hot-spot area scenario

2.2.2 Standalone high frequency

The standalone operation can be considered to apply in the indoor scenarios.

One typical indoor scenario is the office (as shown in Figure 2-3) or residential (as shown in Figure 2-4) area scenarios. Major features of such scenarios include lattice distributed room, moderate building area, moderate user density, large traffic demand, low user mobility. Key challenges to be solved in such scenarios include high demand for indoor throughput, interference management of indoor antennas or interference among micro-cells, high-frequency antenna pattern design and the planning of microcells for indoor.

Figure 2-3: Indoor office scenario

Figure 2-4: Indoor residential area scenario

Another typical indoor scenario includes shopping mall (as shown in Figure 2-5) or train station (as shown in Figure 2-6) scenarios. Key features of such scenarios include large and spacious indoor room with little blockage, high user density, large traffic demand, and low user mobility. Key challenges to be solved in such scenarios include demand for dense connectivity, and indoor throughput, interference management of indoor antennas or interference among micro-cells, high-frequency antenna pattern design and the planning of microcells for indoor.

Figure 2-5: Indoor shopping mall scenario.

Figure 2-6: Indoor train station scenario.

2.2.3 Wireless backhaul

In practical networks, there are needs to build new macro / micro base station in some high traffic areas, wherein it may

however not satisfy the condition to set up fiber transmission to provide wired backhaul to the base station. In this case, high-frequency communications combined with large-scale antenna array technology can be employed to provide wireless backhaul for the new sites, which can solve the high cost problem of deploying a wired backhaul in urban area. Key features of the wireless backhaul scenario include less blockage, large traffic demand, large backhaul bandwidth, and low user mobility. Key challenges to be solved for such scenarios include, demand for high transmission rate, high reliability, low transmission delay, and flexible configuration of backhaul bandwidth.

Figure 2-7: Wireless backhaul scenario

2.2.4 User-centric non-cell (UCNC) Network

In the traditional view, cellular is characterized by “the best general arrangement for the minimum interference and with a minimum number of frequencies is a hexagonal layout in which each station is surrounded by six equidistant stations”. However, the need of enhancing spectral efficiency makes us have to tackle the most challenging target by revisiting the cellular concept.

User-centric no-cell network (UCNC), as a new paradigm of network topology, is expected in 5G communications, either in the lower frequency bands or in the higher frequency bands, as illustrated in Figure 2-8.

Figure 2-8: UCNC network in lower frequency and higher frequency

In the UCNC topology, devices are no longer constrained to a single antenna/base-station, but liked with a cloud of antenna and cloud networks. From a user’s point of view, a group of base stations “serve for” itself. Considering that the directional beam transmission is utilized in mmWave communications, the spectral efficiency can be improved 7-8 times via this kind of network topology.

Figure 2-9: mmWave pencil-beam based UCNC network for indoor deployment scenario

2.3 Channel Characteristics

2.3.1 Measurement results

2.3.1.1 Channel measurement results for 28GHz

Here we introduce a set of high frequency channel measurement results obtained during a channel measurement campaign jointly made by BUPT and CMCC.

2.3.1.1.1 Platform of the measurement

Figure 2-10: Structure of the channel measurement platform

The platform shown in Figure 2-10 is composed of a pair of 8-horn antenna arrays is deployed, which supports omnidirectional MIMO measurement. Specifically, the operation procedures are as follows: at the TX side, modulated specific pseudo-noise (PN) code is generated by the PN sequence generator. Then, it is modulated to the corresponding high frequency after up-conversion. An amplifier is used to increase the signal power up to 30 dBm before proceeding through the antenna switch unit (ASU) with eight outputs. In a certain time sequence, the signal is switched to the 8-horn antennas sequentially. Eventually, it is transmitted into the wireless channel by the transmitting antenna. Accordingly, at

the RX side, the signal is captured by the 8-horn antennas and then converted to baseband signal after down-conversion. Eventually, the baseband signal will be coherently demodulated using a sliding correlator to acquire the channel impulse response (CIR). Displaying the real-time result helps to determine the validity of the raw measurement data that are eventually stored in the prescribed format for post-processing.

2.3.1.1.2 Effects of the rotation step on virtual measurement in hall scenario at 28 GHz

Figure 2-11: Layout of the virtual MIMO measurement scenario

Table 2-4: Comparison of time cost and the number of multipath in the azimuth domain. DR denotes the dynamic range below the peak power in PAS and L is the initialized total number of MPCs in the estimation procedure using the SAGE algorithm

Rotate step	Data acquisition time (min)	Estimation time by SAGE (min)	Estimated MPCs by SAGE ($L = 100$)				
			DR = 35 dB	DR = 30 dB	DR = 25 dB	DR = 20 dB	DR = 15 dB
2°	30	120	91	86	65	44	22
3°	20	105	85	81	63	41	22
5°	12	80	60	54	38	23	13
8°	9	70	59	45	33	24	12
10°	6	60	44	32	25	12	6

Table 2-5: Comparison of RMS angle spread

Rotating step	$\mu_{lg ASA} \lg ASA = \lg(ASA/1^\circ)$
2°	1.67
3°	1.65
5°	1.57
8°	1.45
10°	1.34
3GPP (Indoor, LoS)	1.58

Currently, virtual MIMO measurements are applied prevalently to obtain the spatial characteristics of a channel. The measurements involve setting up the virtual multi-element circular array by rotating a horn antenna to transmit or receive

an omni-directional signal, which can characterize the channel more exactly. However, considering the ambiguity of the rotating step and the HPBW of the directional antenna, it is necessary to pay attention to the effects of the size of the virtual array on the precision of the estimated results in the virtual MIMO measurement. This effect was investigated by conducting a virtual measurement in a typical indoor LoS scenario within BUPT with a biconical antenna at the TX side and a horn antenna at the RX side [2]. The horn antenna has the same HPBW of 10° in both the azimuth and the elevation dimensions [3]. In the measurement, the horn antenna is rotated from 0° to 360° with a rotating step of $\Delta\theta$ in the azimuth dimensions, where $\Delta\theta = 2^\circ, 3^\circ, 5^\circ, 8^\circ, 10^\circ$, such that the adjacent rotations have different visual overlap as shown in Figure 2-11. Empirically, this measurement can be regarded as a $1 \times (360/\Delta\theta)$ MIMO channel measurement. Then, the SAGE algorithm was utilized to extract the channel spatial characteristics to verify whether this algorithm would be as effective as expected. In view of the distribution of the estimated PAS at each rotating step, the consistency with the real scenario differs significantly. The MPCs at the step of 2° are the most, followed by those at the step of 5° , with those at the step of 10° being the least. Table 2-4 presents the exact results, including the time cost during the rotation measurement and the processing procedure of the SAGE algorithm. In addition, the RMS angle spread is a key parameter to characterize the dispersion of MPCs in the spatial domain. Table 2-5 presents the results of the RMS azimuth spread of the arrival angles (ASA). The results in Table 2-5 indicate the average value of ASA displays a decreasing trend as the size of the rotating step is enlarged.

2.3.1.1.3 Estimation of the K-factor in a UMi scenario at 28 GHz

Figure 2-12: measurement layout in the UMi scenario at 28 GHz

Figure 2-13: K-factor statistics under LoS and NLoS conditions, respectively. (a) LoS scenario; (b) NLoS scenario

To obtain the distribution of the high-frequency channel fading, we conducted a measurement with mobility in UMi scenario at 28 GHz [4],[5]. In this scenario, a sectored antenna and an omnidirectional antenna were used to collect the multiple paths. Figure 2-12 shows the layout that was used during measurements, during which the TX was mounted on

the trolley and fixed on the ground. The spacing between the successive measured spots was 2 m. We applied the moment-method to calculate the K-factor in the frequency domain to obtain the K-factor statistics shown in Figure 2-13. We can see that the K-factor (in dB) of both the LoS and NLoS scenarios approximately displays a normal (Gaussian) distribution. In the LoS scenario, the mean value of the fitted normal distribution is 9.51 dB, which is a little larger than the experimental results, i.e., 9 dB, as obtained in [6]. The difference in the measured environment was mainly responsible for the different results. In the NLoS scenario, the mean value of the fitted normal curve is 1.95 dB, which suggests Rician fading rather than Rayleigh fading. This is mainly because of the existence of a dominant and stable component due to the reflections; similar effects have been observed previously below 6 GHz [7].

2.3.1.1.4 Blockage of human body measurement in shopping mall at 28 GHz

Figure 2-14: Measurement environment and setup for 28 GHz HBS

Figure 2-15: Schematic diagram of the measurement scenario. Person moves perpendicularly to LoS path with human body facing either towards TX or perpendicularly to LoS path

Figure 2-16: Human body moves perpendicularly to the LoS path. (a) Human body faced towards TX; (b) human body faced perpendicularly to LoS path.

The influence of HBS was researched by performing a measurement campaign in a typical indoor shopping mall scenario at 28 GHz [8], as shown in Figure 2-14. The results provide a simple model for predicting and analyzing the effect of HBS based on a special case at 28 GHz. In the measurement, a typical case of blocking by a human body was adopted to validate the HBS model and acquire a comprehensive HBS profile. The specific details are presented in Figure 2-15. Then, during further data processing, two methods of double-edge diffraction and multiple-edge diffraction are utilized to analyze the characteristics of HBS, and these two methods and the measured result were compared. As shown in Figure 2-15, in order to study the influence of the direction of the human body and emulate person crossing the LoS path, the person crossed the LoS path vertically at the midpoint of TX and RX, with the body either facing TX or perpendicular to the LoS path, respectively. The results are presented in Figure 2-16 and it is clear that the measured results are in good correspondence with the results of these two models. This illustrates that the received signal is mainly due to diffraction from the vertical edges of the human body. In addition, with the person facing towards TX, the result of the double-edge diffraction method is 3.96 dB smaller than the measured result compared to the multiple-edge of 0.96 dB [9], [10]. These results are mainly attributed to the failure of the diffraction ray to reach the RX because the ray was obstructed by the person's shoulder. Therefore, in this case, the multiple-edge diffraction method is simplified as the double-edge diffraction method. In terms of the shadowing width (SW), which is defined as the width of the area where the shadowing gain is below 0 dB, the SW value of the measured results are 0.8 m and 0.4 m in the two cases, respectively. This result can be well explained when considering that the former has a relatively larger shadowing area compared with the latter.

2.3.1.1.5 Delay characteristics for directional and omni-directional channel measurement in indoor office and shopping mall at 28 GHz

Table 2-6: Parameters of system configuration

Items	Settings
Center Frequency	28 GHz
Chip Rate	400 Mc chips/s
Signal Sampling Rate	1200 MHz
PN Code Length	511
Transmitting Power	30 dBm
Horn Ant. Gain	25 dBi
Horn Ant. AZ. HPBW	10°
Horn Ant. EL. HPBW	10°
Biconical Ant. Gain	12.5 dBi
Biconical Ant. AZ. HPBW	360°
Biconical Ant. EL. HPBW	5°

Figure 2-17: Measurement plan in open office scenario

Figure 2-18: Measurement plan in shopping mall scenario

The channel measurement was conducted with the broadband sliding correlation channel sounder supported by National Instrument. The detailed parameters of system configuration are summarized in Table 2-6. The channel measurements were carried out in two indoor scenarios which are open office and shopping mall and they are corresponding to Figure 2-17 and Figure 2-18. For both the measurements in open office and shopping mall, two kinds of antenna configuration at TX and

RX are explored. One is horn antenna to horn antenna (HA2HA), the other is biconical antenna to biconical antenna (BA2BA). In HA2HA case, the TX and RX antennas are aligned in the direction of the maximum antenna gain. Because the elevation HPBW of biconical antenna is relatively small, both the antennas at TX and RX are set to the same height in order to compare the effect of different antenna configurations.

Figure 2-19: PDF of RMS DS in open office scenario with a log-normal fit

Figure 2-20: PDF of RMS DS in shopping mall scenario with a log-normal fit

The probability density distributions (PDF) of RMS DS of HA2HA and BA2BA cases in open office scenario are shown in Figure 2-19 (a) and (b), respectively. It is obvious that the log-normal distribution fits the RMS DS well both in HA2HA and BA2BA cases in open office scenario. The μ and σ of fitted log-normal distribution are -8.82 and 0.36 in HA2HA case whereas they are -8.25 and 0.46 in BA2BA case. As shown in the figure, the RMS DS of BA2BA case is mainly ranged from 0 ns to 50 ns, which is about 5 times of the range in HA2HA case.

Figure 2-20 illustrates the PDF of RMS DS in both LoS and NLoS conditions of shopping mall scenario. The RMS DS

are all fitted well by log-normal distribution in LoS and NLoS condition for the two antenna configurations. Comparing the RMS DS of HA2HA and BA2BA cases in LoS or NLoS condition, the distribution range of RMS DS of BA2BA is wider than that of HA2HA. It is similar to the situation in open office scenario. The distribution range difference between BA2BA and HA2HA in LoS condition is larger than that in NLoS case. As shown in Figure 2-20 (b) and (d), the μ values of LoS and NLoS conditions in BA2BA case of shopping mall scenario are -7.52 and -7.49. It can be found that the measured rms DS parameter in shopping mall scenario is larger than that of ITU-R M.2135 in LoS case. But there is no much difference between the measurement and ITU-R M.2135 in NLoS case.

Table 2-7: Statistics of delay parameters

Scenarios		Delay Parameters (ns)		
		τ_{rms}	τ_{mean}	τ_{max}
Open Office	HA2HA, LoS	2	25	454
	BA2BA, LoS	12	24	434
Shopping Mall	HA2HA, LoS	3	5	53
	BA2BA, LoS	37	25	350
	HA2HA, NLoS	11	11	125
	BA2BA, NLoS	42	44	314

Table 2-7 summarizes the mean value of delay parameters. For the LoS condition of open office scenario, the RMS DS of BA2BA is 12 ns which is larger than that in HA2HA. But there is no much difference on excess mean delay and maximum excess delay. In shopping mall scenario, an obvious trend can be observed. The delay values in NLoS condition are larger than those in LoS condition for the same antenna configuration. For the same propagation condition, the delay values of HA2HA are smaller than those of BA2BA

2.3.1.2 Channel measurement results for 26GHz & 39GHz

2.3.1.2.1 Platform of the measurement

The measurements are performed using time domain channel detector system [11], shown in Figure 2-21. At the transmitter (TX), a 30dB gain wideband power amplifier (PA) and an biconical horn antenna are used. At the receiver (RX), a horn antenna with 24.3dB gain is applied with 3-dB beam-width of 10°.

Figure 2-21: mmWave measurement platform

The wideband channel sounder can detect signals at frequency range between 10 GHz and 100 GHz, and 2 GHz is the maximum bandwidth for signal generated by the system. Table 2-8 lists the detailed specification of the system used in

indoor office measurements.

Table 2-8: Specification of the system

Parameter	Value
Center frequency	26GHz
Bandwidth	1GHz
Delay boundary	1.024us
Delay resolution	1ns
Tx power	-6dBm
PA power	30dBi
Gain of the horn antenna	24.3dBi
HPBW of the horn antenna	10°
Gain of the biconical horn	3dBi

2.3.1.2.2 Large scale parameters measurement of indoor office at 26 GHz

Figure 2-22: Layout of the indoor office scenario

The measurements are conducted at KeySight Beijing office with an area of more than 2000 m² as shown in

Figure 2-22. A total of one TX and thirty-nine RX locations are set. Full details can be found in [11][15].

Path loss is an important factor to be analyzed and considered for radio system design. Since the rotatable horn antenna are used at the RX in the measurements, two kinds of path loss models are derived based on the measurement, including

directional and mean path loss models by using the directional (lowest) and mean power from 72 azimuth angles with 0° elevation angle.

Figure 2-23: LoS directional and mean path-loss and SF

When deriving the RAS in the elevation plane, the measurement data from locations 29 to 39 are applied. The mean value of the RAS in the elevation plane is 0.77dB (°), and the standard deviation (STD) is 0.1dB (°). The RAS in the azimuth plane shown in Figure 2-24 are derived from all 39 RX locations when the horn is rotated from 0° to 360° with elevation angle of 0°. The mean value is 1.37dB (°), and the STD is 0.19dB (°). Compared with the elevation RAS, the azimuth RAS is larger and can be better fitted into normal distribution.

Figure 2-24: Angular spread comparison of measurement and normal-fit

2.3.1.2.3 Measurements in UMi scenario at 32 GHz

The outdoor microcellular measurements are conducted on campus roads, similar to a street canyon scenario, as shown in Figure 2-25. Full details can be found in [12].

Figure 2-25: Measurement environments.

Figure 2-26 shows the measurement routes, including LoS and NLoS scenarios. The TX and RX are located in a crane and a trolley with heights of 6.1 meter and 1.8 meter respectively, and equipped with an omni-directional antenna and a horn antenna respectively. The horn has a 10° HPBW and is able to rotate in both of the azimuth and elevation planes by using a stepper motor. To obtain the AoA and EOA information, the horn is rotated from 0° to 360° with 5° angular step in the azimuth plane, and several co-elevation angles are selected to repeat such rotating measurement with respect to the distance between the TX and RX.

a) Scenario 1

b) Scenario 2

Figure 2-26: Layout of measurement campaigns

The measurement system parameters are listed in Table 2-9.

Table 2-9: Measurement system parameters.

Parameters	Value
Carrier frequency	32 GHz
Bandwidth	1 GHz
Code length	4096 chips
Delay resolution	1ns
Tx/Rx antenna	Omni-directional / pyramidal horn antenna
Tx/Rx antenna gain	3dB/24 dB
Tx/Rx antenna height	6.1m / 1.8 m
Measured distance(LoS/NLoS)	141 m / 72 m

For the two typical microcell scenarios measured herein, SAGE based parametric method as well as nonparametric method are used to obtain the RMS delay spread and RMS angle spread. The path-loss models and shadow fading by the

CI method are summarized in Table 2-10, wherein the CI model for omni-directional path loss is defined as

$$PL_{dB} = 10 \cdot A \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{1m} \right) + B + C \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{f_c}{1GHz} \right)$$

Table 2-10: Channel parameters

Frequency (GHz)		32 GHz			
Scenario		Outdoor microcells			
		Scenario #1		Scenario #2	
		LoS	NLoS	LoS	NLoS
Path-loss [dB] †	A	2.14	3.83	1.84	3.34
	B	32.4	32.4	32.4	32.4
	C	20	20	20	20
SF [dB]	σ_{SF}	3.5	3.8	0.9	3.0
log(RDS[s])	μ_{DS}	-8.07	-7.95	-7.32	-6.74
	σ_{DS}	0.10	0.40	0.42	0.19
log(ARAS[°])	μ_{ASA}	0.80	1.13	1.33	1.24
	σ_{ASA}	0.27	0.46	0.37	0.38
log(ERAS[°])	μ_{ESA}	0.77	0.80	0.88	0.99
	σ_{ESA}	0.10	0.17	0.15	0.12
N		8	7	8	9
Cluster ARAS[°]		4	3	3	3
Cluster ERAS[°]		8	7	8	8
KF[dB]	μ	7.48	N/A	3.57	N/A
	σ	3.37	N/A	4.35	N/A

2.3.1.2.4 Human Body Attenuation and Trees Material Penetration Loss

Attenuation by human bodies and penetration loss of material at higher frequency bands, are important issues to be taken into account for the design of IMT-2020 wireless systems. Series of measurement are conducted at the bands 24.25-27.5 and 37-40.5GHz. Table 2-11 describes the parameters of measurement system. Full details can be found in [13][14].

Table 2-11: Specification of the system

Parameter	26 GHz	39 GHz
Bandwidth	1 GHz	1 GHz
Maximum delay	1.024 us	1.024 us
Delay resolution	1 ns	1 ns
Tx power	24 dBm	24 dBm
Heights of the Tx/Rx	1.3/1.3 m (human) 6.0/2.0 m (tree)	1.3/1.3 m (human) 6.0/2.0 m (tree)
Gain of the horn antenna	24.3 dBi	27 dBi
Polarization of the horn antenna	Vertical	Vertical
HPBW of the horn antenna	10°	10°

The radio channel measurement campaigns are conducted in a restaurant with an area of around 1000 m². Measurement environment is shown in Figure 2-27.

Figure 2-27: Measurement environments

The following measurement campaigns shown in Figure 2-28, with one to three human bodies with human frontal and lateral crossing the TX–RX connection line, are carried out to investigate human body attenuation.

Figure 2-28: Measurement setup for human body blockage.

Table 2-12 lists the summary of the maximum measured human attenuation and RMSEs between the measured and Volger’s model results at 26 and 39 GHz.

Table 2-12: Human body attenuation at 26 and 39 GHz through crossing

Measurement cases		The RMSE between the measurements and Vogler’s model (dB)		Maximum measured attenuation (dB)	
		26 GHz	39.5 GHz	26 GHz	39 GHz
Lateral crossing	1 person	1.43	1.66	12.66	19.00
	2 persons	2.94	2.11	22.49	26.83
	3 persons	2.74	1.58	28.25	33.98
Frontal crossing	1 person	1.80	1.12	12.53	12.54
	2 persons	1.26	1.55	15.60	19.21
	3 persons	1.53	1.82	21.69	24.54
1 person walking		1.11	1.79	13.91	18.11

Penetration loss for different materials is measured at offices, as shown in Figure 2-29. The received power is measured when the transceiver is in free space and the tested material is placed in between the transceivers; then the power difference is defined as the penetration loss of the material.

(a) Wooden door of the laboratory (b) Transparent glass door of the hall

(c) Frosted glass door of a small office (d) wooden door of the cabinet

Figure 2-29: Penetration loss measurements

Table 2-13 summarizes the penetration loss of different materials with specific thicknesses at 26 and 39GHz, respectively. It is seen that the loss at 39GHz is larger than that at 26GHz for each material in general. From Table 2-13, it is found that the total thickness of the two transparent glass doors of the hall is 25.70mm which is thinner than the wooden door of the laboratory, but their attenuation is almost the same; it may mean that wooden attenuation is smaller than that of transparent glass in the same thickness at 26 and 39GHz, respectively.

Table 2-13: Penetration losses of the materials

Material	Thickness	26 GHz	39 GHz
Wooden door of the laboratory	47.94 mm	5.50 dB	9.69 dB
Transparent glass door of the hall (one door)	12.85 mm	3.95 dB	4.59 dB
Transparent glass door of the hall (two doors)	25.70 mm	5.55 dB	9.45 dB
Frosted glass door of the small office	12.30 mm	4.10 dB	4.65 dB
Wooden door of the cabinet	19.82 mm	4.16 dB	5.59 dB

2.3.1.3 Other measurement results

2.3.1.3.1 Path loss and delay spread measurement of indoor office

Measurements were performed at the China Mobile Research Institute at 3.5, 6, 14, 23, 26 and 28 GHz. The common architecture of channel sounder is designed by Rohde& Schwarz, and different center frequencies mentioned above were set as the center frequency with 250 MHz bandwidth. The length of PN sequence was 216 which was transmitted at the rate of 125 megachips-per-second 90 snapshots were obtained at each measurement spot. Biconical antennas were mounted both in the TX and RX side.

Measurement parameters are summarized in Table 2-14.

Table 2-14: measurement system parameters

Center Frequency	3.5, 6, 14, 23, 26, 28 GHz
Bandwidth	250 MHz
Chip Rate	125 MChips/s
Time Domain Resolution	4 ns
Code Length	2^{16}
Antenna Type	Bi-conical
Transmit power	16 dBm

The channel measurement campaign was carried out on the 21th floor of the Innovation Building in China Mobile Research Institute. Measurements are carried out for LoS and NLoS scenarios respectively, illustrated by Figure 2-30 (a) and Figure 2-30 (b).

Figure 2-30: Layout of indoor scenario

(a) FI path loss model in LOS propagation

(b) FI path loss model in NLOS propagation

Figure 2-31: Floating-intercept path loss at different frequencies in LoS and NLoS environment

Table 2-15: FI path loss models for indoor scenario

Case	Frequency [GHz]	α	β	SF[dB]
LOS	3.5	1.55	44.6	3.1
	6	1.45	51.0	2.8
	14	2.07	52.9	2.3
	23	1.74	58.4	2.0
	26	1.95	58.6	2.5
	28	1.92	61.6	2.2
NLOS	3.5	2.96	35.1	2.8
	6	2.70	45.6	2.0
	14	3.11	49.0	2.8
	23	4.20	37.0	2.3
	26	3.29	49.0	2.9
	28	3.63	48.9	2.9

Table 2-16 Table 2-15: ABG path loss model for indoor scenario

Case	Frequency [GHz]	α	β	γ	SF[dB]
LOS	3.5-28	1.78	29.88	2.21	2.84
NLOS	3.5-28	3.31	18.09	2.23	3.05

(a) ABG path loss model in LOS propagation

(b) ABG path loss model in NLOS propagation

Figure 2-32: Alpha-beta-gamma path loss across different frequencies and distances in LoS and NLoS environment

The FI path loss results derived from measured data in LoS and NLoS cases at each frequency band are shown in **Figure 2-31 (a)** and **Figure 2-31 (b)** respectively. Parameters obtained by FI model are listed in Table 2-15. We can see that all path loss exponents are less than or close to 2 in LoS case. Furthermore, the path loss exponent value ranges from 1.55 at 3.5 GHz to 1.92 at 28 GHz, increasing with frequency. This is partly due to different radio propagation conditions at different frequency bands. Signals received at higher frequency are weaker mainly due to the fact that only direct path and reflection paths are observed.

Then, all data above are fitted by ABG model. The fitting curves can be seen in **Figure 2-32 (a)** and **Figure 2-32 (b)**. Across different frequencies and distances, parameters of ABG path loss model are summarized in Table 2-16. The frequency dependent factors are observed as 2.21 and 2.23 while distance dependent factors are 1.78 and 3.31, in LoS and NLoS case respectively.

(a) RMS delay spread in LOS propagation

(b) RMS delay spread in NLOS propagation

Figure 2-33: RMS delay spread in LoS and NLoS propagation

2.3.1.3.2 Penetration loss measurement and modelling

Among the various channel characteristics, penetration loss is a vital parameter which determines, for example, the ability of the outdoor signal to penetrate into buildings and the indoor signals to penetrate through interior walls. As a result, a number of measurement campaigns have been conducted to study the penetration loss of various materials, particularly in higher frequency bands.

Different materials commonly used in building construction have very diverse penetration loss characteristics. Generally, the materials with lower conductivity, such as common glass and dry wood, would cause lower penetration loss than those materials with higher conductivity, such as metal. Modern building walls are likely composed by several materials such as glass, concrete, brick, wood, as well as metal, which are common used as the support structure, the electrical wires, and socket, etc. These metal materials would produce many reflecting surfaces and hence increase the penetration loss. Some results of a recent measurement campaign for 30GHz frequency band are briefly summarized as following figures and table.

Figure 2-34: Histogram of penetration loss of wooden walls

Figure 2-35. Histogram of penetration loss of drywall

Figure 2-36. Histogram of penetration loss of concrete wall/pillars

Table 2-17: Summarize of penetration loss of some materials

Materials	Thickness (cm)	Penetration loss (dB)
Wood	4.25-28	8.34-15.08
Drywall	6.5-37.25	11.85-53.47
Concrete	19-34.25	31.32-60.11

Many literatures show that penetration loss is frequency dependence parameters and some detailed mathematical analysis has been conducted to explain the relation between the penetration loss and the frequency. According to the electromagnetic propagation theory, when the electromagnetic wave is normally incident on a dielectric slab, as depicted in **Figure 2-37**, it establishes a set of reflected waves and transmitted waves in the two faces of the material. In general, with the increase of frequency, the attenuation in the material tends to increase. On the other hand, the superposition of these reflections at the surfaces of the material determines the total received power. If the in-phase superposition happens, the received power is stronger than the nominal single path. Otherwise, if the superposition is out-of-phase, the received power becomes less than the nominal single path. Since the phase of each transmitted wave changes with the frequency continuously for a material with a fixed thickness, the received power shows a fluctuation behavior with the increase of frequency. Two examples about glass and wood materials are shown in **Figure 2-38** and **Figure 2-39**, respectively. Since the wooden door is composited by different materials, the multiple reflections would be more complex than the homogeneous glass. As a result, the penetration loss of wooden door does not exhibit much regularity in its fluctuations with increasing frequency.

According to the analysis, the penetration loss can be modeled as an ABG model $PL(\text{dB}) = a + b \cdot f(\text{GHz}) + \sigma$, where a and b determine the main frequency dependence and σ is the fit error due to the fluctuation.

Figure 2-37. Illustration of successive reflections and transmissions for penetration.

Figure 2-38. Penetration loss measurement results of single layer glass.

Figure 2-39. Penetration loss measurement results of wooden door.

Incidence angle is another factor affected the penetration loss. In general, larger incidence angle would cause higher penetration loss due to the longer penetration path. According to the literature, increase the incidence angle can result in up to 15-20 dB additional penetration loss in the worst case.

2.3.1.3.3 MIMO channel measurement at 73GHz

In the millimeter wave communication, the higher gain antenna with narrow beam width is used to compensate the propagation attenuation. Utilizing narrow beams, the spatial MIMO is a significant feature in the millimeter wave communication system. In order to study the millimeter wave MIMO channel characteristic, a measurement campaign is held by HUAWEI as depicted in **Figure 2-40**. A mechanical auto scan shelf is used to shift the antenna in a tiny step less than half wavelength. In the measurement campaign, the receiver is mounted on the scan shelf and the transmitter is mounted on a fixed shelf and not moving. Thus, a SIMO channel measurement is completed. The measurement scenario is an indoor meeting room that can be shown in the **Figure 2-41**. The measurement frequency is 73 GHz. A self-developed 4-D MIMO channel estimation algorithm is implemented to extract the channel path for the indoor SIMO scenario. The

channel estimation results are depicted in the Table 2-18: 73 GHz indoor SIMO channel estimation result

Figure 2-40 SIMO mechanical auto scan shelf

Figure 2-41 SIMO measurement scenario

Table 2-18: 73 GHz indoor SIMO channel estimation result

	ZoA(degree)	AoA(degree)	power(dB)	delay(ns)
1	5.3124	127.4268	-59.2601	24.4079
2	16.2289	-100.5573	-71.8446	25.6057
3	5.5293	-51.8314	-80.8941	24.9256
4	17.0865	168.4966	-83.7506	31.7395

Additionally, different array size is measured to analysis the capacity for the SIMO system as shown in Figure 2-42. For the SISO case, the estimated channel capacity is about 0.688 bits/s/Hz larger than ergodic capacity at 20dB SNR. When the receiver array size increase, the estimated channel capacity trends to be equal to the ergodic capacity of Rayleigh fading

channel.

Figure 2-42 MIMO capacity result

2.3.1.3.4 Channel consistency between multiple frequency bands

In the 5G heterogeneous network, an open problem is the coordination between LF and HF radio links. In 3GPP, a uniform air interface has been designed for the full spectrum from 0.5GHz to 100GHz in 5G, including the frame structure in uplink and downlink, OFDM-based waveforms, physical channels, and multiple antenna transmission mechanisms etc. This paves the way for the coordinated HF and LF links. A fundamental question is how the channels in LF and HF are consistent or correlated with each other, such as power angular spectrum, channel impulse response, path loss etc. Strongly correlated channels between LF and HF are supportive to develop new techniques for coordinated LF and HF. For example, the overhead of beam training in HF links is expected to be optimized in aid of the channel information obtained from LF links, suppose both LF and HF links are co-locating in transmitter and receiver.

A measurement campaign was held by HUAWEI to measure the channel correlation between LF and HF under different cases. The measurement layout can be found in the **Figure 2-43**. Four different case, LoS, sparse foliage, density foliage, and NLoS are studied in this campaign.

Figure 2-43: channel consistency measurement scenario

Table 2-19 lists the strongest propagation path of LF and HF for the LoS, foliage and NLoS case. in the LoS case, there

is only 10° offset for LF and HF propagation angular path, it indicates a high correlation of the LoS channel between LF and HF. In the foliage case, sparse and density foliage case have different correlation characteristic. In the sparse foliage case, there is 10° to 20° offset for LF and HF propagation angular path, that indicate a weak LF and HF channel correlation at the sparse foliage case. In the density foliage and NLoS case, there is up to 30° to 40° offset for LF and HF propagation angular path and the channel correlation between LF and HF is bad.

Table 2-19: the strongest AoA path for LoS, foliage and NLoS case

Position	3.5GHz	28GHz	Difference	Scan overhead
LOS [AoA(degree), ZoA(degree)]				
RX1	[10,10]	[10,20]	[0,10]	[0,20]
RX2	[-10,20]	[0,20]	[10,0]	[20,0]
RX3	[0,10]	[10,20]	[10,10]	[20,20]
RX4	[0,10]	[0,20]	[0,10]	[0,20]
RX5	[0,20]	[20,10]	[20,10]	[40,20]
Sparse Foliage [AoA(degree), ZoA(degree)]				
RX6	[20,0]	[10,20]	[10,20]	[20,40]
RX7	[10,0]	[20,10]	[10,10]	[20,20]
Density Foliage [AoA(degree), ZoA(degree)]				
RX8	[-20,-10]	[10,10]	[30,20]	[60,40]
RX9	[30,-10]	[0,-10]	[30,0]	[60,0]
RX12	[30,0]	[10,-10]	[20,10]	[40,20]
NLOS [AoA(degree), ZoA(degree)]				
RX10	[160,-20]	[-160,10]	[40,30]	[80,60]
RX11	[-170,0]	[-160,10]	[10,10]	[20,20]

2.3.2 Channel Model

2.3.2.1 Channel model in 3GPP

To fulfill ITU's 5G requirements, 3GPP has started the study of New Radio (NR) technologies since 2016. As mmWave is considered as an important spectrum resource to be exploited by NR, 3GPP established a channel model study item, targeting at establishing a representative and feasible channel model for the evaluation and verification of NR technologies. Based on a large amount of channel measurement inputs and the subsequent signaling processing, 3GPP has managed to complete a channel model covering frequency range from 0.5GHz to 100GHz

The channel model is a geometry based stochastic channel model (GSCM). Channel is generated in a step-wise

approach, as follows.

- Set general parameters, e.g., scenario, LoS/NLoS condition, pathloss and large scale parameters;
- Generate small scale parameters, e.g., delays, cluster powers, arrival and departure angles, coupling of rays, XPRs;
- Generate channel coefficients according.

In addition to the above mentioned general channel descriptions. Several additional features have been captured to reflect new channel characteristics, especially for high frequency band.

At high frequency band, channel attenuation is sensitive to foliage, atmosphere and rain attenuations. Those are considered as additional contribution factor to the shadowing. For 60GHz band, an additional oxygen absorption model is established.

High frequency channel is also sensitive to the dynamic blockage, e.g., human-body, vehicle, etc. Measurement results show that even human body blockage may lead to up to 20 dB channel attenuation. In 3GPP channel model, a specific blockage model is established.

The new channel model is also made more consistent in temporal, frequency and spatial domain, to fulfill the new radio evaluation requirement of very wide bandwidth (e.g., >1GHz), very high sampling rate, very large antenna array; as well as obtain more realistic evaluation results for technologies like MU-MIMO or V2X, wherein non-modelling of the spatial correlation may generate unrealistic evaluation results.

2.3.2.2 Channel model for ITU

Figure 2-44: The IMT-2020 Channel model family for evaluation

The IMT-2020 channel model includes a Primary Module, a Map-based Hybrid Channel Module and an Extension Module, as seen in Figure 2-44. Firstly, the primary channel module is a set of geometry-based stochastic channel model. Secondly, Map-based hybrid channel model is available as an alternative channel modelling methodology. Thirdly,

Extension module below 6 GHz, as an optional method of generating the channel parameters, follows Extension module of evaluated report in the IMT-Advanced period. Finally, a summary of advanced modelling components is show in the evaluated report, which is a brilliant guide to describe.

ITU-R WP5D also defined channel models for link-level evaluations, including CDL and TDL, wherein the frequency range is from 0.5GHz to 100GHz. In the evaluated report, there are five candidate link-level channel modes for CDL/TDL separately. More importantly, there is one-to-one correspondence between ITU-R's and 3GPP's in the link-level channel model's numerology, their characteristics and parameters. For example, defination of CDL/TDL-i in ITU-R is simliar with CDL/TDL-A's in the 3GPP. Finally, in order to some technology performance requirements, a mapping relationship between test environments and link-level channel model can be found in the Table 2-20.

Table 2-20: link-level channel model for ITU-R WP5D

Parameters	Indoor Hotspot-eMBB	Dense Urban-eMBB	Rural-eMBB	Urban Macro-mMTC	Urban Macro-URLLC
Link-level Channel model	NLoS: CDL/TDL-i LoS: CDL/TDL-iv	NLoS: CDL/TDL-iii LoS: CDL/TDL-v	NLoS: CDL/TDL-iii LoS: CDL/TDL-v	NLoS: TDL-iii LoS: TDL-v	NLoS: TDL-iii LoS: TDL-v

2.4 System design and key technologies

2.4.1 Hybrid high-low Band wireless access

2.4.1.1 Introduction

In this subsection we study an ultra-broadband wireless access utilizing both of the new frequency bands at 28 GHz and 3.5 GHz. In order to deliver very high rates to indoor users, the only installation requirement envisioned is that the user places an indoor modem and antenna somewhere close to windows. We are targeting very high throughputs (e.g. 100 Mbps) delivered wirelessly via transmitters located in outdoor to most of the indoor locations (e.g. 95% of the targeted indoor area) through a simultaneous use of high and low spectrum bands.

The existing licensed bandwidths within the low spectrum bands are usually capped. Although there is more bandwidth at high bands the propagation is much more challenging. Moreover, obstructions such as trees, cars and houses have a much more significant effect [17][18][19][20][21][22][27]. A very dense network required at high frequency bands may not be economically feasible. For large scale deployments, we show that it is beneficial to supplement the high spectrum band deployments with sites operating at low spectrum bands but serving only selected users. If well architected, a low carrier frequency deployment helps to provide sufficiently high data rates (e.g., tens to hundreds of Mbps) to users present at locations corresponding to more challenging radio conditions, due to their better propagation properties through lossy environments. This relaxes the constraint on the site-to-site distance, which makes the solution more economical and attractive.

The proposed hybrid multi-carrier deployments leverage the strengths of low and high spectrum bands together and results in an ultra-broadband wireless access system that meets the high expectations for capacity, coverage and user experience. The key ingredients consist of:

- Intelligently balancing the traffic load across radio spectrum bands
- Designing for larger inter-site distances to ease the economic feasibility of the proposed solution

2.4.1.2 Morphology and system modeling

We have created a representative 3D model of a dense suburban neighborhood in New Jersey. Figure 2-45 shows the top view of the 3D suburban environment model:

Figure 2-45: Suburban environment model: Blue dots show the locations of 13 cell sites which are simultaneously active and placed with a 228 m Inter-Site-Distance (ISD) on three parallel streets.

In this representative model, each house covers an area of 0.14 acres in a density of 1683 houses per km². There are 13 simultaneously active sites placed on three parallel streets with a reference Inter-Site-Distance (ISD) of 228 m. The sites are staggered on parallel streets by half ISD (114 m) to reduce the cross-site interference. To avoid border effects, we collect statistics from the 94 houses that are within the magenta shaded area. Further, we assume two scenarios for the traffic density, with 12 or 5 simultaneously active users at each site.

Figure 2-46 shows the detailed view of the same suburban environment. Each house, 7 m tall, has a layout of two floors with five windows on each floor overlooking the street and the backyard. We also accounted for street obstructions such as trees, cars and utility poles. The utility poles are 12 m tall and are placed every 38 m on both sides of each street. We consider a default site deployment configuration with cell sites that are attached to every sixth utility pole, at a height of 9 m above ground. There are two rows of trees on the backyards, and there is a tree and a parked car in front of each house. The canopies and trunks of each tree may significantly impact the radio propagation characteristics and are approximated by rectangular boxes in this model. The trees are 8 m tall with a ground clearance of 2.5 m. We assume 9 dB transmission loss through the canopy of the tree and 24 dB transmission loss through the trunk of the tree at 28 GHz [18][25][26][27]. The signals do not penetrate well through the exterior of the building at high bands due to the short wave lengths as shown in previous measurement studies [22][28]. Therefore, we set the transmission loss through the exterior wall to 60 dB at 28 GHz and 12 dB at 3.5 GHz. Further, we added cars as supplemental obstructions on both directions on streets as well as the parked cars, to capture reasonably well a typical suburban environment. Cars are modeled as metallic boxes with glass windows.

The most important means of signal penetration to indoor serviced areas from outdoor transmitters is generally through windows. The penetration and reflection loss through windows is set to at 4.6 dB and 4.9 dB at 28 GHz, respectively; for 3.5 GHz they are 5.2 dB and 4.2 dB, respectively. Noticeably, the frequencies 28 GHz, 3.5 GHz have similar transmission and reflection coefficients at incidence angles close to the normal angle, which is encouraging for outdoor to indoor penetration at higher frequencies[21][28]. Higher losses are reported for tinted windows[28][29]. The reference [27] discusses more the propagation characteristics of this environment in greater detail.

Figure 2-46: Detailed 3D View

We consider three deployment strategies: (i) single RAT at 28 GHz, (ii) single RAT at 3.5 GHz, and (iii) hybrid deployment with both RATs enabled at 28 GHz and 3.5 GHz.

Single RAT - 28 GHz (250 MHz available bandwidth): For better in-building penetration at 28 GHz and to compensate for the additional 18 dB path loss at 28 GHz in comparison to 3.5 GHz, we considered directional beams with 15° horizontal and vertical beamwidth and 25 dBi gain. These beams are pointing at 24 different directions with 15° separation in azimuth. We consider the case where only 4 beams are simultaneously active at a time and share the 1 W available power per 250 MHz equally. The noise figure is set to 5 dB.

Single RAT - 3.5 GHz (40 MHz available bandwidth): At 3.5 GHz we used directional beams characterized by 13° horizontal beamwidth, 8° vertical beamwidth and 19 dBi gain. Similar to the high band, these beams are also pointing at 24 different directions with 15° separation. We again consider the case where only 4 beams are active at a time and share equally the 1 W available power per 40 MHz. The noise figure is set to 5 dB.

Hybrid Deployment - High Band and Low Band (28 GHz, 250 MHz available bandwidth; 3.5 GHz, 40 MHz available bandwidth): Each site has both RATs available. The active users are assigned to RATs so that their cell edge rate (e.g., identified as the 5% of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of user rates) is maximized. We use a quality control threshold which may be updated in an online manner, depending on the number of active users, number of active beams and radio conditions to assign users to either band. As an example, houses which receive a power level above a tunable quality control threshold (e.g., -83 dBm) may connect preferentially to the 28 GHz RAT (subject to cross-band load balancing). The other houses attach to the 3.5 GHz RAT.

2.4.1.3 Results

a) Coverage and sustained throughput at 228 m ISD

Figure 2-47: Received power comparison: Single RAT and Hybrid

Figure 2-47 shows the comparison of received power between the single RAT and hybrid deployments. Single RAT deployment at 28 GHz is limited in terms of coverage at the cell edge. The power levels at the 5% of the CDF curves are -101 dBm, -81 dBm and -71 dBm for the 28 GHz, hybrid and 3.5 GHz deployments, respectively. For the single 28 GHz RAT, the signal strength is below the noise level of -85 dBm for 32% of the locations. On the other hand, the single 3.5 GHz RAT deployment has the best propagation properties and all locations receive a signal above the noise level of -93 dBm.

Figure 2-48 shows the comparison of SINR and SNR for each deployment. The SINR is -17 dB, 4 dB and 10 dB at 5% of the CDF for the 28 GHz, hybrid and 3.5 GHz deployments, respectively. At the median of the CDF, the SINR is 6 dB, 14 dB and 20 dB for the 28 GHz, hybrid and 3.5 GHz deployments, respectively. The largest gap between SINR and SNR CDFs corresponds to the 3.5 GHz deployment: the 18 dB gap at the median and the larger gap in general clearly indicates that this deployment suffers significantly from interference. Nevertheless, note that the 3.5 GHz system has a large SINR even at cell edge unlike traditional cellular systems because of the use of narrow beams.

On the other hand, the 28 GHz deployment is mostly noise limited, as the SNR and SINR CDFs almost overlap. We further notice that 33% of locations receive an SINR that is less than 0 dB for the deployment at 28 GHz. The lower SINR region of the hybrid deployment CDF is primarily attributed to user locations connected through the 28 GHz RAT; the CDFs of SNR and SINR are again very close to each other in that range. This is supported through the detailed distributions illustrated in Figure 2-49, which shows the CDFs of SINR and SNR resulting from grouping separately the locations connected to 3.5 GHz and 28 GHz for the hybrid deployment. This clearly shows that all locations at the 5% of the SINR CDF are attached to the 28 GHz band.

Figure 2-48: SNR, SINR comparison: Single RAT and Hybrid

Figure 2-49: Hybrid deployment, SINR, SNR per frequency band

Figure 2-50 contrasts the CDFs of the sustained throughput per house achieved through the three deployments under the assumption that there are 12 simultaneously active users per site. In hybrid deployment houses which receive a power level above the optimized quality control threshold of -83 dBm are assigned to 28 GHz. The sustained throughput for the 28 GHz deployment is limited to 1 Mbps at 5% (cell edge) on the CDF, but it grows to 115 Mbps and 472 Mbps at the median and 95% on the CDF, respectively as shown in Fig. 7. Since the 28 GHz deployment is limited in terms coverage at the edge considering a much larger bandwidth than 250 MHz would not be beneficial to increase the throughput significantly. The deployment at 3.5 GHz yields better cell edge throughput, with 32 Mbps at the 5% of the CDF, but it is capped to 78

Mbps at best, due to the limited available bandwidth of 40 MHz. On the other hand, the hybrid deployment combines the strengths of both low and high frequency bands. Fewer users (compared to single 3.5 GHz deployment) share the available bandwidth at 3.5 GHz, yielding a threefold throughput gain at the 5% over a disjoint operation across the two bands, i.e. 99 Mbps versus 33 Mbps.

Figure 2-50: Sustained throughput comparison between single RAT and hybrid deployments

The benefits of the hybrid deployment are also clearly visible at median and 95th percentile. The users in better radio conditions share the larger available bandwidth at 28 GHz without the need to compete for resources with users in poor radio conditions (e.g., cell edge). These enhancements are visible in the median rate (202 Mbps) and at the 95% (756 Mbps) of the CDF of the sustained user rates. The decomposition of the user throughputs per individual band indicated that most cell edge locations (within the 5% of the CDF) connect to 28 GHz, due to the larger available bandwidth, which yields higher rates in spite of lower SINR values compared to the 3.5 GHz conditions.

Table 2-21 shows the tabulated results corresponding to the 5%, median (50%) and 95% levels of the CDF distributions of user throughputs for single RAT and hybrid deployments. To evaluate the impact of the traffic load on the system performance, we have considered two user densities, with 12 and 5 simultaneous active users per site. For the scenario with 12 active users per site we have employed the default assumption of four simultaneous active beams per site per RAT. The same system configuration assumption was made for the scenario with lighter traffic load, except for the hybrid deployment, where only two beams were simultaneously active for the 3.5 GHz RAT, in order to limit the likelihood of interference while sweeping beams. This is intuitively easy to understand, as there are still six active beams in total operating across the two RATs to serve the 5 users of the lighter traffic load scenario. The three columns in the middle correspond to default placement (the modem is placed anywhere within 3 m away from windows). The last three columns correspond to the case where the modem is assumed to be placed with some care. It is modeled as the location corresponding to the median radio conditions. Comparison of the results indicates that the cell edge performance may be enhanced if a sample of signal strength measurements is taken, and the modem is placed with some care, instead of a simple random placement. On the other hand, a placement of the modem at a location corresponding to the median radio conditions measured in the premise, naturally limits the high percentile throughputs since it does not favor either extreme of the performance range.

Table 2-21: Sustained Throughput Per Site at 228 m ISD

User Density	Frequency	Number of Simultaneous Active Beams		Per House Sustained Throughput [Mbps] All Receivers			Per House Sustained Throughput [Mbps] House Median Front& Back		
		28 GHz	3.5 GHz	5%	Median	95%	5%	Median	95%
12 Active Users per Site	28 GHz	4	-	1	115	472	25	121	376
	3.5 GHz	-	4	32	63	78	51	63	71
	Hybrid	4	4	99	202	756	163	203	601
5 Active Users per Site	28 GHz	4	-	3	277	1133	61	291	901
	3.5 GHz	-	4	77	150	186	122	152	170
	Hybrid	4	2	185	346	1417	230	364	1127

b) Sensitivity to EIRP Increase

Figure 2-51: Sensitivity to total transmitted power.

Figure 2-51 illustrates the dependency of the sustained user throughput on the transmitted power level, which was varied within the range of 250 mW to 10 W. A decrease by 6 dB from the default 1 W power level causes a drop in the cell edge rate from 99 Mbps to 66 Mbps. On the other hand, increasing the total transmitted power by 6 dB over the default 1 W power level yields a rate enhancement from 99 Mbps to 125 Mbps at the cell edge. Increasing further the transmitted power level up to 10 W has marginal effect on the cell edge increase for the single RAT 28 GHz deployment, and cell edge rates as high as 100 Mbps are not feasible through this deployment. On the other hand, the median rates for both single RAT 28 GHz and hybrid deployments do increase significantly with increase of the transmitted power level, since the 28 GHz deployment with 228 m ISD is primarily limited by noise. The single RAT 3.5 GHz deployment does not benefit from increasing the transmitted power level beyond the default 1 W, since it is mostly interference limited, both at cell edge and median locations.

c) Cell Sites Densification

This section addresses the impact of site densification on the system performance. System configurations considered for this analysis are described in Table 2-22. In addition to the default ISD of 228 m, we have also considered an ISD of 152 m and 76 m. The hybrid deployment requires two radios, one for each RAT; the 3.5 GHz RAT radios are always spaced out with a 228 m ISD, while the 28 GHz RAT radios are spaced out with varying ISD. The same reference traffic load of 12 simultaneously active users per site with an ISD of 228 m was maintained while varying the ISD of the 28 GHz system. The number of simultaneously active beams was selected for each system configuration out of several candidate configurations, based on capacity and interference considerations. For instance, the number of simultaneously active beams was reduced to 3 for both single RAT deployments with the ISD of 76 m. This is because this configuration has more sites to absorb the same traffic volume compared to the ISD of 228 m case; this in turn helps increase the available power per active beam, since the total 1W available power is divided among the number of active beams. Similar considerations for minimizing the number of active beams were applied to the hybrid deployment; the configurations listed in Table 2-22 yielded the best achievable sustained throughputs out of all configurations with up to 4 simultaneous active beams per site per RAT. Figure 2-52 shows the 5% and median sustained throughputs for the configurations in Table 2-22. For the single RAT 28 GHz deployments, the sustained throughputs at the cell edge are 1 Mbps, 10 Mbps and 111 Mbps for an ISD of 228 m, 152 m, and 76 m, respectively. On the other hand, single RAT 3.5 GHz deployments benefit less from the site densification due to the lower available bandwidth (40 MHz): the sustained throughputs at the cell edge are 32 Mbps, 43 Mbps and 62 Mbps for an ISD of 228 m, 152 m, and 76 m, respectively. Even the best 95% of the sustained throughput CDF with 76 m ISD is capped at 164 Mbps.

Table 2-22: Number of simultaneous active beams versus ISD

Deployment	ISD at 3.5 GHz	ISD at 28 GHz	Number of simultaneous active beams	
			28 GHz	3.5 GHz
Single RAT 28 GHz		228 m	4	
		152 m	4	
		76 m	3	
Single RAT 3.5 GHz	228 m			4
	152 m			4
	76 m			3
Hybrid	228 m	228 m	4	4
	228 m	152 m	4	2
	228 m	76 m	3	1

Figure 2-52: Sustained throughput per house at 76 m, 152 m and 228 m ISD, 12 active users at 228 m.

Figure 2-53: Sustained throughput per house, 1 active user per cell site.

The same figure highlights the benefits of a hybrid deployment. One can reach sustained throughputs on the order of 100 Mbps at the cell edge either through a 28 GHz only system with an ISD of 76 m or through a hybrid deployment with an ISD of 228 m. Thanks to the reduced number of required cell sites, the hybrid deployments are much more economically attractive. Also note that both median and 95% of the sustained throughputs increase significantly with site densification, due to the fact that the 28 GHz is primarily limited by noise.

Figure 2-53 shows the time-averaged peak throughput per house at 5%, median and 95% CDF percentile for single RAT 28 GHz and hybrid deployments, with ISD of 228 m, 152 m and 76 m, and under the assumption that there is a single user active per cell site. Consequently, only 1 active beam per RAT is required for these configurations. The throughputs at median and 95% rates are similar for single RAT 28 GHz and hybrid deployments. This is because for the hybrid deployment operating at lighter loads, the users at the median and 95% of the CDF tend to connect to the 28 GHz RAT. Lastly, we can note that 1 Gbps sustained throughputs are feasible at least for some users.

2.4.1.4 Summary

We study the design of an ultra-broadband wireless system. We showed that a hybrid low band (3.5 GHz) and high band (28 GHz) wireless system, with cell sites deployed outdoor may provide broadband wireless connectivity to indoor users with indoor antennas close to the windows. Such hybrid deployments improve the cell edge performance with less cell site densification than a 28 GHz system alone. Via 3D ray tracing simulations, we demonstrated that sustained user throughputs as high as 100 Mbps per house are feasible. Moreover, these deployments yield better rates at the cell edge, since fewer users share the limited bandwidth available at 3.5 GHz (40 MHz assumed in this analysis). They also yield better median and peak rates, thanks to the larger available spectrum at the high 28 GHz band (250 MHz assumed in this analysis). Moreover, hybrid deployments are also more resilient to environmental uncertainties, thanks to the better propagation at the low 3.5 GHz band. Obstructions from trees and cars have a significant effect, and have been factored into account to a certain extent using 3D ray tracing tool. We further show that the rates achieved through such hybrid deployments may be boosted, either through an increase in EIRP or through site densification.

Specifically, we showed that minimum rates of 99 Mbps are feasible for 95% of all receiver locations with such hybrid deployments (228 m ISD and 12 simultaneously active users per cell site). Further, we showed sustained throughputs of 347 Mbps at the cell edge for configurations with an increased cell site density (ISD of 76 m).

In comparison, a single 28 GHz only deployment performs poorly at the cell edge for a configuration with an ISD of 228 m. With such a ISD, the 28 GHz RAT is mostly noise limited. For this reason, further cell site densification at 28 GHz does improve the cell edge rates as well as the median rates. On the other hand, the 3.5 GHz only deployment is interference limited. Because of interference, beamforming at 3.5 GHz is critical to achieve high cell edge SINR and high data rates.

A key take away of the analysis is that sustained throughputs on the order of 100 Mbps at the cell edge are feasible, either through a single 28 GHz high band RAT with cell site densification (76m ISD) or through a hybrid deployment combining the 28 GHz high band and the 3.5 GHz low band operating with a larger site-to-site distance (228m ISD).

Finally, one should note that additional reliability and throughput enhancements are possible with higher transmit antenna gain and receive antenna gain (0 dBi in the current model), using different polarizations, and higher transmit power to compensate for additional obstructions.

2.4.2 Beam management

2.4.2.1 Motivation

Design of beam management should consider impact of HF channel properties. Some parts of which are shown in Figure 2–54. deriving from indoor real-field HF channel measurement, where the half-power beamwidth of probing TX/RX beam is 15 degree. The following observations are derived:

- Multiple paths with significant power are sparsely distributed in spatial domain.
- Desirable beam pairs (with dominant received power) are cluster-alike around dominant propagation paths.
- Channel properties with regards to those closed beam pairs are highly correlated.

Consequently, in order to achieve spatial multiplexing, diversity, beam maintenance and alternative beam related

indication, these correlations of channel properties (including channel response, angles of arrival and departure, QCL and TA.) for these pairs should be explicitly or implicitly indicated in beam management, to be more specific, involving beam reporting, determination and indication.

Figure 2-54: Received RSRP for probing beam pair in the high frequency

2.4.2.2 Use cases

In HF, multi-beam based operation is supported at both TRP and UE sides. Given the pre-specified beam patterns exist, beam management, which generally targets to identify the optimal pattern for data transmission in real time, should be considered in beam-based transmission with the following four typical cases as shown in Figure 2-55:

- Case 1: Beam pair(s) acquisition
- Case 2: Beam pair(s) based transmission
- Case 3: Beam pair(s) maintenance (or gradual changing)
- Case 4: Alternative beam based switching (or abrupt changing)

Figure 2-55: Beam management scenarios

For Case 1: The TRP and UE are to sweep the selective beams and subsequently determine the one or multiple beam pairs corresponding to significant paths. These training results would become the resource pool of beam pairs for control/data channels.

For Case 2: The TRP and UE select the pairs for control/data transmission according to the results of beam pair(s) acquisition in case 1. Other selected pairs can be considered as alternatives, e.g., against the unexpected blockage, in the following two cases.

For Case 3: Owing to possible UE rotation and movement, the TRP and UE need to update or maintain their transmission pair(s) via gradual sweeping/refinement. The serving beam pair is updated after more suitable beam is found.

For Case 4: When channel blockage occurs, the procedures listed in Case 3 would not be sufficient since the current link has been dramatically degraded. The TRP and UE would indicate the beam pair(s) from alternative pool(s) for subsequent transmission pair, after probing these candidates in order to prevent outage.

The concept of beam-group based beam management is to manage beams in group basis instead of beam-by-beam basis. The beam management procedure including group based indication/reporting, beam-group maintenance and transmission group(s) switching is shown in Figure 2-56. Notes that only mainly recommended procedures of grouping-based beam management are summarized here.

- **Step 1 Beam sweeping:** Reference signals (RSs) associated with one or more TX beams, such as CSI-RS, DMRS, are transmitted via numerous time/frequency resources, and these RSs are received by UE for measuring channel properties with one or more RX beams.
- **Step 2 UE-centric beam grouping:** UE groups DL TX beams according to channel/beam properties observed by UE, e.g., quasi-co-location (QCL) properties, angle of arrival for DL, delay, etc. With beam grouping at UE side, UE also can help TRP to identify multi-path observed by the UE and let TRP know the UE beam information implicitly, i.e., UE can group beams according to each UE's beamforming implementation/capability.
- **Step 3 Grouping-based UE reporting:** UE carries out one beam feedback report for K beam group, and beam report includes $N * \text{logical beam index}$ (i.e., N-best beam) + RSRP/CSI with the best beam + group ID per beam group.
- **Step 4 Grouping-based beam indication:** TRP should configure the QCL relationship among swept beams according to grouping information of UE reporting and its beamforming capability. Deriving QCL assumptions between group ID(s) and the subsequent transmission/measurement beam-related RSs are to assist UE-side

beamforming/reception as beam indication. This beam indication is conducted via multi-stage indication for QCL among RS ports, via joint using RRC, MAC-CE and DCI signaling.

- **Step 5 Group(s) maintenance for beam refinement:** The group-related reference signal with or without grouping indication signaling is to be triggered by UEs/TRP with the explicitly configurable or fixed number of sweeping beams, which also can be used for beam refinement or beam tracking. It is noted that after beam sweeping, the group(s) of TRP and UE remain but its related beam might be changed accordingly, which is agnostic to other side.
- **Step 6 Transmission group(s) switching for beam recovery:** In the case that link qualities are lower than expectations, TRP and UE would directly probe these alternative ones with grouping indication before switching groups for data/control channel and subsequently determining whether switching its transmission group(s) to alternative one or not accordingly. It means that the data stream would be transmitted continuously without outage.

Figure 2-56: Group-based beam management.

2.4.3 Limited Feedback Hybrid beamforming for frequency selective channel

In this section, we describe a limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm for frequency-selective channel. Simulation results validate theoretical expressions.

2.4.3.1 System model

We consider a multi-user and multi-carrier hybrid analog-digital MIMO-OFDM system with N antennas configured on the base station and U single-antenna users, as shown in Figure 2-57.

Figure 2-57: Block diagram of hybrid analog-digital MIMO-OFDM system

Assume the OFDM system has N_f subcarriers, all of which are allocated to the users, and the considered system has N_a RF chains. In each symbol period, U symbols are transmitted at each subcarrier. Therefore, the total number of the symbols transmitted in each period is $U \times N_f$ [30].

The transmitted symbol matrix is denoted by $\mathbf{D} = [\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{N_f}]$, where $\mathbf{d}_i = [\mathbf{d}_{1,i}, \mathbf{d}_{2,i}, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{U,i}]^T$, and $\mathbf{d}_{u,i}$ represents the symbol transmitted to the u^{th} user at the i^{th} subcarrier. Given that the digital precoding is before the IFFT operation and the analog precoding is after the IFFT operation, let $\mathbf{F}_{BB,i} \in \mathcal{C}^{N_a \times U}$ represents the digital precoding matrix of the i^{th} subcarrier and $\mathbf{F}_{RF} \in \mathcal{C}^{N \times N_a}$ represents the subcarrier-common analog precoding matrix. Then, at the i^{th} subcarrier, the received signal at of u^{th} user can be expressed as [30][31][32][33]

$$\hat{d}_{u,i} = \mathbf{h}_{u,i} \mathbf{F}_{RF} \mathbf{F}_{BB,i} \mathbf{d}_i + n_{u,i}, \forall u, i \quad (2-1)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{u,i} \in \mathcal{C}^{1 \times N}$ represents the channel coefficient matrix between the u^{th} user and the base station at the i^{th} subcarrier and $n_{u,i}$ represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ_n^2 .

2.4.3.2 Limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm for flat-fading channel

As it is not practical to obtain global channel knowledge at the transmitter in mmWave communication, a limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm for flat-fading channel is proposed in [34]. This algorithm requires low training overhead and small feedback overhead.

In [34], the downlink mmWave system was considered with the base-station employing hybrid analog/digital

architecture and mobile users having analog-only combining as depicted in Figure 2-58.

Figure 2-58: System model for the multiuser hybrid precoding design

For this system, a two-stage hybrid precoding algorithm was proposed and proved to achieve a near-optimal performance compared to a certain full-digital approach. At the first stage, the analog beamformer and combiner are designed to maximize the power at each user by single-user beam-training, neglecting the resulting interference among users. At the second stage, the baseband precoder is designed from the channel estimates performed at the MS side to reduce inter-user interference. Only effective channels need to be trained, due to dimensionality reduction. The performance of multi-user mmWave systems with limited feedback for flat-fading channel was also studied in [34].

2.4.3.3 Limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm for frequency selective channel

In the previous section, a limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm is introduced for flat-fading channel. MmWave systems, however, will likely operate on wideband channels with frequency selectivity. Therefore, a multi-user limited feedback hybrid beamforming algorithm for frequency selective channel is proposed in this section, while it will not increase the number of RF chains compared with the flat-fading case.

For each subcarrier, the BS can obtain the optimal beamforming codewords with narrow beams for each user. By summing the N_f optimal beamforming codewords, the proposed algorithm can broaden the beams, which can satisfy all the subcarriers.

Algorithm 1: Proposed Hybrid Beamforming Algorithm

Input : \mathbf{F} | BS RF beamforming codebook

First stage : RF beamforming design

For each subcarrier i , $i = 1, \dots, N_f$ and each MS u , $u = 1, \dots, U$

The BS and MS u select $\mathbf{v}_{u,i}$ that solve

$$\mathbf{v}_{u,i} = \arg \max_{\forall \mathbf{v}_{u,i} \in \mathbf{F}} \|\mathbf{h}_{u,i} \mathbf{v}_{u,i}\|$$

$$\text{BS sets } \mathbf{f}_u = \frac{1}{N_f} \sum_{i=1}^{N_f} \mathbf{v}_{u,i}, \quad \mathbf{F}_{RF} = [\mathbf{f}_1, \mathbf{f}_2, \dots, \mathbf{f}_U]$$

Second stage : Digital precoding design

For each subcarrier i , $i = 1, \dots, N_f$ and each MS u , $u = 1, \dots, U$

MS estimates its effective channel $\widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{u,i} = \mathbf{h}_{u,i} \mathbf{F}_{RF}$

MS quantizes $\widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{u,i}$ using a codebook \mathbf{H} and feeds it back

For each subcarrier i , $i = 1, \dots, N_f$

$$\text{BS sets } \mathbf{F}_{BB,i} = \overline{\mathbf{H}_i^* (\mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{H}_i^*)^{-1} \mathbf{H}_i} = [\widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{1,i}, \widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{2,i}, \dots, \widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{U,i}]^T$$

$$\text{BS normalizes } \mathbf{f}_{u,i}^{BB} = \frac{\mathbf{f}_{u,i}^{BB}}{\|\mathbf{F}_{RF} \mathbf{f}_{u,i}^{BB}\|}, \quad u = 1, \dots, U, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_f \quad (2-2)$$

Get $\mathbf{F}_{BB,i}$, $i = 1, \dots, N_f$

Algorithm 1 can be summarized as follows. In the first stage, at the i^{th} subcarrier, the BS design the RF beamforming vectors, $\mathbf{v}_{u,i}$, to maximize the desired signal power for user u , and neglect the other users' interference. As this is the typical RF beamforming design problem, efficient beam training algorithms developed for flat-fading channel such as [34][35][36], can be used to design the RF beamforming vectors at each subcarrier. Then, at all subcarriers, we derive the RF beamforming vectors for user u as

$$\mathbf{f}_u = \frac{1}{N_f} \sum_{i=1}^{N_f} \mathbf{v}_{u,i} \quad (2-3)$$

The m^{th} row and n^{th} element of matrix \mathbf{F}_{RF} can be written as $a_{mn} e^{j\phi_{mn}}$, where $0 \leq a_{mn} \leq 1$. Then $a_{mn} e^{j\phi_{mn}}$ can be expresses as [30]

$$a_{mn} e^{j\phi_{mn}} = e^{j \left(\cos^{-1} \left(\frac{a_{mn}}{2} \right) + \phi_{mn} \right)} + e^{-j \left(\cos^{-1} \left(\frac{a_{mn}}{2} \right) - \phi_{mn} \right)} \quad (2-4)$$

According the equation (1-4), each element of \mathbf{F}_{RF} can be equivalently expressed as the sum of two digital phase shifters.

In the second stage, at i^{th} subcarrier, the BS trains the effective channels, $\mathbf{h}_{u,i} = \mathbf{h}_{u,i} \mathbf{F}_{RF}$, $u = 1, 2, \dots, U$. Then each MS u quantizes its effective channel using a codebook, and feeds the index of the quantized channel vector back to the BS. Finally, the BS designs its zero-forcing digital precoder based on the quantized channels at each subcarrier [34].

2.4.3.4 Simulation results and analysis

In all simulations, we employ the geometric channel model [30][36][37][38][39]. Parameters in all simulations are summarized as follows. The number of the transmit antennas is $N=128$, the number of the receiver antennas is $n_r=1$, the number of users is $U=4$, the number of the RF chains is $N_a=U=4$. All plots are generated by averaging over 1000 channel realizations.

In this simulation, we examine and compare the performances of the proposed hybrid beamforming algorithm for frequency selective channel and the existing hybrid beamforming algorithm for flat-fading channel. To this end, we set the number of the subcarrier is $N_f=2$. Figure 2-59 shows that the proposed hybrid beamforming can operate on frequency selective channel at the cost of little performance degradation, but the existing hybrid beamforming only can operate on flat-fading channel.

Figure 2-59: The per subcarrier average sum rate of proposed HB

Figure 2-60 shows the impact of the number of the subcarriers on the per subcarrier average sum rate for the proposed HB. As shown in Figure 2-60 with increasing the number of subcarriers, the per subcarrier average sum rate degrades.

Figure 2-60: Impact of the number of subcarrier on per subcarrier average sum rate of proposed HB

2.4.4 Hybrid beamforming design for mmWave OFDM communication system

For MIMO communication system, especially MU-MIMO, the accuracy of CSI obtained at the network layer will directly determine the accuracy of precoding and the efficiency of the scheduling algorithm, then affecting the overall system performance. Thus, the acquisition of CSI has always been one of the most important problems in MIMO technology standardization processing.

According to the present signal structure in LTE, reference signals are all arranged in the baseband, so CSI required for digital precoding can be obtained via channel estimation. In hybrid beamforming architecture, due to analog beamforming introduced, the number of equivalent digital channels is far less than the actual number of antennas, and the dimension of the channel matrix obtained via reference signals is much lower than the complete channel matrix associated to all antennas. Therefore, subjecting to the number of RF chains, the performance of low-dimensional digital precoding inevitably affords to some loss, in comparison to the one with complete channel matrix. Furthermore, for the analog beamforming section, the procedure is closer to the physical antenna side, and then its MIMO channel has a higher degree of freedom. However, in mmWave communication system, it is too time costly for entry-wise estimation of the channel matrix, which has a large scale due to large antenna arrays. Furthermore, since it is difficult to arrange reference signals whose dimension matches up with the number of antennas, no matter FDD or TDD, and due to quantization errors, imperfections in the channel estimation process and limited, delayed or noisy feedback from the receivers, perfect CSI cannot be directly obtained. This motivates us to consider the hybrid beamforming design without CSI knowledge to solve this problem.

In practical scenarios, the wireless communication channel is usually not quasi-static frequency-flat Rayleigh fading channel. In most practical realization, the wireless communication channel has frequency selective property. Especially in the mmWave communication system, the fading channel has a very high chance to be frequency selective owing to the extremely large transmission scale. In order to alleviate the adverse effects of frequency selective channel fading, mmWave communication system can be implemented with the aid of orthogonal frequency division multiplex (OFDM) technique.

In this section, for the convenience of comparison, we introduce a codebook-based two-stage hybrid beamforming algorithm. A novel hybrid digital-analog beamforming algorithm with uplink training is then proposed for TDD OFDM mmWave communication systems. Owing to uplink training, the proposed algorithm can obtain analog beamforming matrix and digital beamforming matrix without CSI knowledge.

2.4.4.1 Codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding method

Here we review a codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding method for massive MIMO, which is considered as conventional hybrid beamforming algorithm. Consider the multi-user mmWave system with hybrid beamforming architecture. A base station with N_t antennas and M RF chains is assumed to communicate with K single-antenna users, as follows.

Figure 2-61: Massive hybrid digital-analog system model

This algorithm works following to the procedure as depicted in Figure 2-61.

Detailed operations are presented by:

First, BS needs to broadcast all codebook vectors in turn.

Here, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ is the index of users, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{code}$ is the index of codebook vectors.

1-A) There are two ways to approximate the channel.

1-A-a) Based on Saleh-Valebzuela channel model, given the azimuth (θ_k, φ_k) of k th user, it's reasonable to obtain the path of LoS, and regard it as the channel of k th user.

1-A-b) Based on the received codebook vectors of k th user, $\mathbf{y}_{k,i} = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{n}_k$, calculate $\mathbf{v}_{k,i^*} = \arg \max_i \|\mathbf{y}_{k,i}\| \approx \arg \max_i \|\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{v}_i\|$, so the approximate channel is denoted as $\mathbf{H}_k \approx \mathbf{v}_{k,i^*}^H$.

1-B) For each user, evaluate all of codebook vectors based on SNR/SINR criterion independently.

1-B-a) Compute SNR: $SNR_{k,i} = \rho |\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{v}_i|^2$

1-B-b) Compute SINR: $SINR_{k,i} = \frac{|\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{v}_i|^2}{\rho + \sum_{j \neq i} |\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{v}_j|^2}$

1-C) For each user, N_{code} SNR/SINR values are obtained. Select M maximum SNR/SINR

Figure 2-62: Procedure of Codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding method.

and corresponding codebook vectors index, then feedback.

1-C-a) Only feedback the index of selected codebook vectors.

1-C-b) Feedback the index of selected codebook vectors and SNR/SINR values.

2-A) BS receives feedback from all users, and obtains the weighting matrix after counting. There are two ways to assess the analog beamforming matrix. For example, $K = 4$, $M = 4$, $N_{code} = 10$.

2-A-a) Calculate the weighting sum of each codebook vector, and select M codebook vectors corresponding to the M biggest weighting sum, as illustrated in Table 2-23.

2-A-b) Calculate the capacity of all users responding to each codebook vector, and select M codebook vectors corresponding to the M biggest capacity, as illustrated Table 2-24.

According to selected M codebook vectors, eventually form analog matrix \mathbf{A} .

2-B) After having the equivalent channel, digital beamforming matrix \mathbf{D} can be calculated by ZF, MMSE etc. There are two ways to obtain the equivalent channel as followed.

2-B-a) Conventional methods in TDD system or FDD system.

2-B-b) Utilizing 1-A-a) or 1-A-b), get the channel estimation, then $\mathbf{H}_{eq} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{A}$.

Eventually, the outputs of the procedure are analog and digital beamforming matrix, **A** and **D**.

Actually, the process of the above-mentioned algorithm is divided into two stages, and then time delay overhead is beyond the average, making this algorithm disagreeable. And placing the computation of all codebook vectors and the channel estimation at the user side, which exacerbates the complexity cost and power consumption of users. Further, rough channel estimation worsens the performance.

Table 2-23: Example of calculating the weighting sum

Codebook vector	v1	v2	v3	v4	v5	v6	v7	v8	v9	v10
User1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
User2	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
User3	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
User4	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
User5	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Weighting sum	5	2	4	3	4	3	2	3	4	3

Table 2-24. Example of calculating the capacity

Codebook vector	v1	v2	v3	v4	v5	v6	v7	v8	v9	v10
User1	51	67	15	72	0	92	78	0	40	0
User2	15	40	57	5	0	0	1	0	25	36
User3	0	2	65	95	77	60	4	0	0	69
User4	0	26	10	88	0	38	60	2	64	0
User5	16	0	56	0	54	0	11	58	23	20
Capacity	82	135	203	260	131	190	154	60	152	125

2.4.4.2 Hybrid digital-analog beamforming algorithm with uplink training in mmWave OFDM system

In mmWave OFDM communication system, we assume that the system has N_f independent subcarriers. With the assumption of the TDD massive system, the uplink and downlink operate in the same frequency band, so the uplink channel and the downlink channel is reciprocal [42]. Thus, we propose a novel hybrid digital-analog beamforming algorithm, via uplink training, and CSI knowledge is totally unnecessary. With uplink training sequence in a certain length, BS can adaptively calculate the analog beamforming matrix and digital beamforming matrix in the m -th subcarrier, e.g. **A**, **D_m** respectively. Note that the analog beamforming matrix **A** should be the same for all subcarriers, because the analog beamformer cannot be implemented separately for each subcarrier. Using the channel reciprocity, it is reasonable to regard

\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{D}_m as beamforming matrices for downlink data transmission.

Actually, in uplink training stage, BS aims to achieve the optimal estimation of users' training sequences known in advance. Utilizing least square method, BS can obtain the optimal beamforming matrix $\mathbf{W}_{opt,m} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_m$ for the m -th subcarrier. This renders the hybrid beamforming design as a matrix factorization problem with unit modulus constraints imposed by the phase shifters. In this algorithm, we try to cancel interfering signals in the analog domain. For this case, the key point of orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) [40][41][42] is applied to find \mathbf{A} for all the subcarriers. Given $\mathbf{W}_{opt,m}$ and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{D}_m can be obtained with no difficulty in the form of least square solution, or other methods.

Consider the multi-user mmWave system where a base station with N_{BS} antennas and N_{RF} RF chains is assumed to communicate with K single-antenna users. First, in the m -th subcarrier, each user transmits the training sequence independently, and at the BS, the received signal is represented by

$$\mathbf{x}_m = \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{s}_m + \mathbf{n}_m \quad (2-5)$$

Where \mathbf{H}_m is the frequency flat fading channel matrix of all users for the m -th subcarrier, \mathbf{n}_m represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) vector. $\mathbf{s}_m = [s_{m,1}, s_{m,2}, \dots, s_{m,K}]^T$ is the training sequence, and $s_{m,k} \in \mathcal{C}^{1 \times L}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ (L -training length) is k -th user's sequence.

Given observations \mathbf{x}_m , our goal is to obtain the estimation $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_m$ of the desired user signal \mathbf{s}_m . Thus, let \mathbf{W}_m be optimal beamforming matrix, then the digital beamforming output is

$$\mathbf{y}_m = \mathbf{W}_m^H \mathbf{x}_m \quad (2-6)$$

And we consider the minimum mean-square error (MMSE) criterion to solve this problem [43], then the objective function is

$$\mathbf{W}_{opt,m} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}_m} E \left\| \mathbf{s}_m - \mathbf{W}_m^H \mathbf{x}_m \right\|^2 \quad (2-7)$$

As is well known, the solution is given by the Wiener beamformer[44]

$$\mathbf{W}_{opt,m} = \mathbf{C}_{xx,m}^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{xs,m} \quad (2-8)$$

Where $\mathbf{C}_{xx,m} = E(\mathbf{x}_m \mathbf{x}_m^H)$ is the covariance matrix of received signal in the m -th subcarrier, and $\mathbf{C}_{xs,m}$ denotes the cross-correlation matrix between received signal and reference signal, composed of each user's cross-correlation vector,

$$\mathbf{C}_{xs,m} = [\mathbf{C}_{xs_1,m}, \mathbf{C}_{xs_2,m}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_{xs_K,m}]^T = E \left([\mathbf{x}_m \mathbf{s}_{1,m}^H, \mathbf{x}_m \mathbf{s}_{2,m}^H, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m \mathbf{s}_{1,m}^H]^T \right) \quad (2-9)$$

If we regard $\mathbf{W}_{opt,m}$ as jointly optimal analog-digital beamforming matrix, then the objective function is rendered into

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A}_{opt}, \mathbf{D}_{opt,m}) &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{D}_m} \left\| \mathbf{W}_{opt,m} - \mathbf{A}_{opt} \mathbf{D}_{opt,m} \right\|_F \\ s.t. \quad &\mathbf{A}_{opt} \in \mathbf{F} \\ &\left\| \mathbf{A}_{opt} \mathbf{D}_{opt,m} \right\|_F^2 = K \end{aligned} \quad (2-10)$$

Where \mathbf{F} is the set of codebook vectors with unit modulus.

Analog beamforming design

For analog precoding design, the main obstacles are the unit modulus constraints, which are intrinsically non-convex. And there is no general approach to solve optimally. In the following, we will adopt the concept of OMP algorithm to find a near-optimal analog beamforming matrix. OMP is the most widely used algorithm, which often offers reasonably good performance. This algorithm requires the columns of analog beamforming matrix to be selected from certain candidate codebook vectors. In this case, we propose a low-complexity algorithm, via introducing QR decomposition to revise OMP algorithm, as **Algorithm 1**. In the **Algorithm 1**, the matrix Ψ_{all} is the matrix contains all of elements of \mathbf{F} as its columns.

Algorithm 1: Analog beamforming algorithm

Given: $\mathbf{W}_{\text{opt},m}$, $\mathbf{F} = \{\psi_n\}_{n=1}^N$

Initial: $\mathbf{A}^{(0)} = [\]$, $\mathbf{W}_{\text{rec},m}^{(0)} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt},m}$

Recursion: for $i = 1, \dots, N_{RF}$

for $m = 1, \dots, N_f$

$$\Omega_m = \Psi_{\text{all}}^T \mathbf{W}_{\text{rec},m}^{(i-1)}$$

end

$$v = \arg \max_{\psi_n \in \mathbf{F}} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{N_f} \Omega_m \Omega_m^H \right)_{n,n}$$

$$\mathbf{A}^{(i)} = [\mathbf{A}^{(i-1)} \ \psi_v]$$

$$QR \text{ decomposition: } \mathbf{A}^{(i)} = \mathbf{Q}^{(i)} \mathbf{R}^{(i)}$$

for $m = 1, \dots, N_f$

$$\text{Update: } \mathbf{W}_{\text{rec},m}^{(i)} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{rec},m}^{(i-1)} - \mathbf{Q}^{(i)} \mathbf{Q}^{(i)H} \mathbf{W}_{\text{rec},m}^{(i-1)}$$

end

end

Get \mathbf{A}

(2-11)

Digital beamforming design

When \mathbf{A} is given, if the power constraint is temporarily removed, the objective function (2-11) is simplified as

$$\mathbf{D}_{0,m} = \underset{\mathbf{D}_m}{\text{minimize}} \left\| \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt},m} - \mathbf{A} \mathbf{D}_m \right\|_F \quad (2-12)$$

which has a well-known least squares solution given by

$$\mathbf{D}_{0,m} = \mathbf{A}^\dagger \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt},m} = \left(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{W}_{\text{opt},m} \quad (2-13)$$

In fact, we can acquire an approximate solution by using the objective function (2-10) to calculate \mathbf{D}_m .

$$\mathbf{D}_{1,m} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{D}_m} E \left\| \mathbf{s}_m - \mathbf{D}_m^H \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{x}_m \right\|^2 \quad (2-14)$$

Similarly, own to the Wiener beamformer [44], the solution is given by

$$\mathbf{D}_{1,m} = \left(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{C}_{xx,m} \mathbf{A} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{C}_{xs,m} \quad (2-15)$$

After theoretical analysis, we know that $\mathbf{D}_{1,m}$ is not as well as $\mathbf{D}_{0,m}$ performs, but almost close. In the process of solving $\mathbf{D}_{1,m}$, multiplying an unrestrained matrix on both sides of the equation may lead to the solution loose. Simulation results have confirmed.

Comparing to the afore-mentioned codebook-based two-stage hybrid beamforming algorithms, this proposed algorithm has several excellent advantages.

(1) Benefitting from the channel reciprocity, this algorithm is based on uplink training to reduce the number of information exchange between BS and UE, resulting in less time delay.

(2) Feedback is undesired and replaced by uplink training via training sequences or sounding reference signals, even pilot signals.

(3) The analog matrix consists of candidate codebook vectors, not as impractical as PZF requires phase shifters with infinite resolution.

(4) The computation and search of candidate codebook vectors are arranged at BS, not UE, saving the cost and power consumption of UE. And BS obtains all users' information, which is available to cancel inter-user interference. Note that in the reference codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding algorithm, UE cannot exchange information with each other, thus the calculated SNR/SINR is actually based on inter-codebook vectors, not inter-user.

(5) The proposed algorithm provides a better sum rate average over all the N_f subcarriers than the single carrier codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding method. In other words, the total sum rate of the proposed algorithm is more than N_f times of that of the codebook-based two-stage hybrid digital-analog precoding method.

In further delicate investigations, we will consider several promising orientations. First, the digital beamforming matrix is normalized by columns of joint beamforming matrix, which means power is equally allocated for each user. However, the channel quality of each user differs. This causes certainly performance loss. Normalization with adaptive power allocation will be rather appropriate. Secondly, the design of training sequence will be another potential. In proposed algorithm, for simplicity, training sequences are generated randomly. Orthogonal or quasi-orthogonal sequences maybe make it easier to cancel inter-user interference in the analog domain.

2.4.4.3 Simulation results and analysis

In this section, we will investigate the performance of the proposed hybrid beamforming algorithms with different configurations. The channel adopts the Saleh-Valebzuela geometric channel model as previously described.

As Figure 2-63 and Figure 2-64 depicted, here comparing proposed algorithm with 32, 64, 128 antennas when the number of users is 4 and 8 and the number of subcarriers is 1 and 2, respectively. It is indicated that the proposed algorithm with a single subcarrier absolutely outperforms the two subcarriers case. Due to the structure of OFDM system, the analog beamformer for the two subcarriers case is rather a compromised scheme than the optimal beamformer for each subcarrier. As a result, the performance of the system will degrade with the increasing number of the subcarriers. The same conclusion can be obtained from Figure 2-64 with 8 users. Furthermore, it is obvious that the capacity of the system with 8 users is larger than that of the system with 4 users.

Figure 2-63: Comparison of proposed algorithm with 1 and 2 subcarriers in 4 users case

Figure 2-64: Comparison of proposed algorithm with 1 and 2 subcarriers in 8 users case

3. Visible Light Communications

Li-Fi may refer to visible light communication (VLC), or optical wireless communications (OWC), which uses visible light (frequency between 400 and 800 THz, or wavelength between 375–780 nm) to transmit binary data in the form of light pulses. This data transmission is both ambient and detectable by other optical devices that act as photodiodes. In brief, VLC technology provides both communication and illumination functionalities.

The technology uses the frequencies generated by LED bulbs, which flicker on and off imperceptibly thousands of times a second to beam information through the air, leading it to be dubbed the digital equivalent of Morse Code. Like Wi-Fi, Li-Fi is wireless and uses similar 802.11 protocols; but it uses visible light communication (instead of radio frequency waves), which has much wider bandwidth.

One big advantage of Li-Fi, short for “light fidelity”, is its lightning speed, faster than Wi-Fi, which uses radio waves to transmit data. Laboratory experiments have shown theoretical transmission speed of over 200 Gbps, fast enough to download 23 DVDs in one second.

What makes Li-Fi relatively exciting compared to other technologies within the same market space is that Li-Fi is practical, granular, easy to implement for indoor geo-location solutions.

There are already products on the market, e.g., Li-Flame by PureLi-Fi, providing light and connectivity in a single device. With further development of the Li-Fi technology, we will expect more mature commercial and industrial solutions in the market.

With faster connectivity and high-speed data transmission, it also opens an interesting space for new businesses. The integration of internet of things devices and Li-Fi will provide a wealth of opportunities for retailers and other businesses alike. For example, shop owners can use Li-Fi to transmit data to multiple customers’ phones quickly, securely and remotely. In the future, Li-Fi will be deployed worldwide, for a cleaner, greener and brighter future.

Figure 3-1: Spectrum.

3.1 Visible Light Spectrum Analysis

Visible light waves are the only portion of electromagnetic waves that is visible to the human eyes. Electromagnetic radiation in this range of wavelengths is called visible light. When visible light shines through a prism, the light is broken apart into the colors of the visible light spectrum. Water vapor in the atmosphere can also break apart wavelengths creating a rainbow. Each color has a different wavelength. Red has the longest wavelength and violet has the shortest wavelength. When all the waves are seen together, they make white light. A typical human eye will respond to wavelengths from about 380 to 750 nm. In terms of frequency, this corresponds to a band in the vicinity of 400–789 THz. The wavelength and the corresponding frequency of each color light are listed in Table 3-1.

Although the visible light has a huge spectrum, it has not been divided into lots of small bands for different applications in visible light communications. Only a few lighting devices that emit monochromatic light can be manufactured. Nevertheless, the wavelength of monochromatic light changes as the working temperate changes causing color shift. Researchers have reached certain consensus that the blue light is more suitable than the other color light in the underwater scenario. But there is no more research conclusion on the spectrum analysis of visible light communications. As the white lighting devices are expected to provide illumination and communication, the visible light spectrum has been utilized as an entire spectrum in visible light communications.

Table 3-1: wavelength and frequency of each color light

Color	Wavelength	Frequency
Violet	380-450nm	669-789THz
Blue	450-495nm	606-668THz
Green	495-570nm	526-606THz
Yellow	570-590nm	508-526THz
Orange	590-620nm	484-508THz
Red	620-750nm	400-484THz

3.2 Deployment scenario

Visible light communications can be applied to various environments. In this section, we present several potential deployment scenarios of visible light communication systems.

3.2.1 Indoor

The Wi-Fi technology has grown rapidly, but still cannot catch up with the demand for wireless data. Some VLC applications for indoor scenario are presented in Figure 3-2. VLC can provide data rates greatly in excess of current Wi-Fi and this can be done at low cost since the RF components and antenna system have been eliminated. By pointing a visible light at another device, one can create a very high speed data link with inherent security. This overcomes the problems of

having to pair or connect and provides a much higher data rate than Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. The ability to send data quickly and in a secure way is the key to many applications. The fact that the visible light cannot be detected on the other side of a wall had great security advantages.

Figure 3-2: Indoor scenarios-(a) home and (b) office

3.2.2 Large public area scenarios

Each visible light information source can be uniquely identified, so the location of any VLC device can be identified quickly and accurately. The positioning application can be deployed in the public area shown in Figure 3-3.

Figure 3-3: Large public area scenarios-(a) parking garage, (b) supermarket, (c) museum and (d) Expo

3.2.3 EMI environment scenarios

Radio is undesirable in passenger compartments of aircraft. LEDs are already used for illumination and can also be used instead of wires to provide media services to passengers. VLC are suitable to be applied in hospitals and in healthcare. Mobile phones and Wi-Fi's are undesirable in certain parts of hospitals, especially around MRI scanners and in operating theatres. Communicating in areas where there is risk of explosions can be a problem (e.g. in mines, petro-chemical plants, oil rigs etc.). VLC can be a safe technique for providing both illumination and communications in the EMI environments shown in Figure 3-4.

Figure 3-4: EMI environment scenarios-(a) cabin, (b) hospital and (c) nuclear power plant

3.2.4 Outdoor scenarios

Two applications that can be deployed in outdoor scenario is briefly depicted in Figure 3-5. Traffic signage, traffic lights, and street lamps are adopting the LED technology so there are massive applications opportunities here. All kinds of services, information broadcasting, positioning, navigation, internet access, would be provided between lighting equipment and vehicles, vehicles and vehicles. It can be used to backhaul traffic between ultra-dense network nodes (UDN), UDN aggregation nodes (UAN) in the third/fourth-generation (3G/4G) networks.

Figure 3-5: Outdoor scenario-(a) Transportation (b) Backhaul/Fronthaul

3.3 Channel characteristics

3.3.1 Typical frequency response of commercial LEDs

In order to explore the transmission capacity of VLC, we first investigate the available bandwidth of commercial LEDs. The frequency response of a commercial LED has been shown in Figure 3-6. The sweeping frequency signals from 1MHz to 100MHz are transmitted by a single LED chip. Obviously, the optical signal power attenuates dramatically as the signal frequency increases. Moreover, the curves of frequency response not only roll down smoothly but also fluctuate largely in the high frequency range (40MHz~100MHz). Hence, one of the most severe problems is to obtain a range of flat and large spectrum as much as possible.

In this experiment, different DC voltages are added onto the LED. The voltages (28V~24V) are represented by red, green, yellow, purple and blue curves in Fig. 3-1. The bandwidths of 3dB, 10dB and 20dB applied by different DC voltages are recorded in Table 3-2. We find that higher DC voltage leads to larger bandwidth for 10dB and 20dB bandwidth cases.

White light emitted by commercial LEDs is usually generated using blue LEDs with yellow phosphor. However, yellow phosphor slows down the switching response of the white LEDs. Thus, blue light optical filter is employed in front of the photodiode to detect the faster response component (blue light). Figure 3-7 shows the frequency response with the use of blue light optical filter. With the assist of optical filter, the 3dB, 10dB and 20dB bandwidths of this LED are extended respectively, and they are recorded in Table 3-3. It is note that optical lens is used to concentrate light signals because blue light optical filter largely reduces the received optical power.

Figure 3-6: Frequency response of a commercial LED

Table 3-2: 3dB, 10dB, 20dB bandwidth of a commercial LED under different DC voltage

DC (V)	Bandwidth (MHz)		
	3dB	10dB	20dB
28	1.2	4.35	18.4
27	1.2	4.35	18.25
26	1.2	4.35	14.21
25	1.2	4.2	11.21
24	1.2	3.3	8.21

Figure 3-7: Frequency response of a commercial LED with the use of blue light optical filter

Table 3-3: 3dB, 10dB, 20dB bandwidth of a commercial LED under different DC voltage with the use of blue light optical filter

DC(V)	Bandwidth(MHz)		
	3dB	10dB	20dB
28	4.27	20.98	54.15
27	4.27	19.03	52.97
26	4.12	15.14	43.83
25	3.22	11.09	33.04
24	2.32	7.94	25.1

3.3.2 Typical models for channel characterization

3.3.2.1 Impulse response

The impulse response should be adopted to characterize the optical wireless channel in the time domain. The channel between the source and the receiver consists of line of sight (LoS) path and non-line of sight (NLoS) path caused by reflection from walls and furniture. The impulse response of a LoS path is given by [45],

$$h^{(0)}(t; S; R) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{d^2} A_R I(\theta) \cos \varphi_0 \delta(t - \frac{d_0}{c}), & 0 \leq \varphi_0 \leq FOV \\ 0, & \varphi_0 \geq FOV \end{cases} \quad (3-1)$$

where A_R is the effective receiver area, d_0 is the direct distance from source S to receiver R, and φ_0 is the angle of incidence on the receiver location. FOV is the field of view of the receiver and c is the speed of light. $I(\theta)$ is radiant intensity in units of Candelas, and θ is the spherical polar angle off normal axis (degrees). $I(\theta)$ depends on the type of optical source. Conventionally, the angular output power of an optical source is typically modelled by a generalized Lambertian pattern having uniaxial symmetry. The intensity is proportional to the viewing angle,

$$I(\theta) = \frac{(m+1)}{2\pi} \cos^m \theta \quad (3-2)$$

The index m is given by $m = \ln(2) / \ln(\cos \theta_{1/2})$ [45][46], where $\theta_{1/2}$ is the source semi-angle at half intensity.

The impulse response containing one bounce path can be written as

$$h^{(1)}(t; S, \varepsilon_i, R) = \begin{cases} h^{(0)}(t; S, \varepsilon_i) \otimes \rho_i \frac{1}{\pi d_{i,2}^2} A_R \cos \theta_2 \cos \varphi_2 \delta(t - \frac{d_{i,2}}{c}), & 0 \leq \varphi_2 \leq FOV \\ 0, & \varphi_2 \geq FOV \end{cases} \quad (3-3)$$

where ρ_i is the reflectivity of the surface ε_i and \otimes is convolution operation. The distance between reflection

surface ε_i and receiver R is denoted by $d_{i,2}$. θ_2 is the irradiance angle of the reflected optical signal and φ_2 is the incidence angle on the receiver R .

The impulse response of k ($k > 0$) bounces can be calculated recursively

$$h^{(k)}(t; S, R) = \sum_{i=0}^N h^{(0)}(t; S, \varepsilon_i) \otimes h^{(k-1)}(t; \varepsilon_i, R) \quad (3-4)$$

The emitted light can reach the receiver after any number of reflections, which can be written as an infinite sum [47],

$$h(t; S, R) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} h^{(k)}(t; S, R) \quad (3-5)$$

where $h^{(k)}(t; S, R)$ is the impulse response of the light undergoing k reflections. Actually, simulations and experiments [48] have shown the total optical power of signals undergoing 4 and more bounces is so small that it can be ignored without any effect.

3.3.2.2 Frequency response

In addition, the frequency response $H(f)$ is the Fourier transform of the channel impulse response $h(t)$, which is given by

$$H(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t) e^{-j2\pi ft} dt \quad (3-6)$$

Note that the frequency response of the dispersive optical wireless channel exhibits a low pass characteristic in the electrical domain. Theoretically, the achievable transmission bandwidth of optical wireless channel can be used to calculate the channel capacity. In practice, the 3-dB channel transmission bandwidth is presented by

$$|H(f_{-3dB})|^2 = 0.5 |H(0)|^2 \quad (3-7)$$

Generally, the 3-dB transmission bandwidth is analyzed at typical receiver locations.

3.3.2.3 Root mean square (RMS) delay spread

Inter-symbol interference (ISI) caused by multipath propagation can be measured by the RMS delay spread. The performance of an optical wireless system is quite sensitive to the RMS delay spread [45]. The RMS delay of the collected signal can be used to numerically compare the temporal dispersion of different channels, and it is evaluated by the simulated channel impulse response. The RMS delay D , of the collected signal is calculated by,

$$D = \left[\frac{\int (t - \mu)^2 h^2(t) dt}{\int h^2(t) dt} \right]^{1/2} \quad (3-8)$$

where the mean excess delay μ can be computed by the following expression:

$$\mu = \left[\frac{\int th^2(t)dt}{\int h^2(t)dt} \right] \quad (3-9)$$

3.3.2.4 Optical path loss

OPL should be adopted to describe the attenuation of the optical signal due to the propagation and reflection in an indoor environment [45][46]. If the sensitivity of a detector is given, the required emitting optical power mainly depends on the OPL of channel. The multipath OPL is defined by the logarithm of direct current (DC) value of the channel transfer function, and the optical dB (dBo) form is given by

$$OPL_{dBo} = -10\log_{10} H(0) \quad (3-10)$$

where the channel DC gain can be calculated by the frequency response $H(0) = \int h(t)dt$ [45][46].

3.3.3 Channel analysis of small indoor scenarios with ideal lighting source

An indoor scenario, which is commonly used, has been shown in Figure 3-8: An indoor scenario with one LED and three receiver positions. In order to investigate the OWC channel characteristics, the transmitter and receiver are usually employed in a room with size of $5 \times 5 \times 3$. The reflectance of walls and ceiling are 0.8, and the reflectance of floor is 0.3. One LED source (transmitter) with Lambertian pattern is employed at the center of the ceiling. Generally, the source is modeled as a point. The direction is vertically downwards. Only one receiver is placed on the floor. The main parameters for the simulation are listed in

Table 3-4.

Figure 3-8: An indoor scenario with one LED and three receiver positions

Table 3-4: Simulation parameters

Parameters		Values
Room:	Size	$5 \times 5 \times 3$
	Reflectance of ceiling	0.8
	Reflectance of walls	0.8
	Reflectance of floor	0.3
	Impulse response time resolution	0.2ns
LED:	Coordinates of LED	(2.5, 2.5, 3)
	Elevation	90°
	Azimuth	0°
	Height	3m
	Transmitted optical power	1W
Receiver:	Coordinates of center position	(2.5, 2.5, 0)
	Coordinates of side position	(2.5, 0.1, 0)
	Coordinates of corner position	(0.1, 0.1, 0)
	Detection area	0.01m^2
	FOV	$30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 85^\circ$
	Elevation	90°
	Azimuth	0°
Height	0m	

3.3.3.1 Impulse response

Figure 3-9: Impulse responses of channel characteristic at the center, side, corner positions with different field of view (FOV)

Table 3-5: Percentage of the quantity of interest to the whole impulse response (%)

	PD position	LoS	1 st Reflection	2 nd Reflection	3 rd Reflection
FOV=30°	Central	94.46%	0%	4.02%	1.52%
	Side	0%	39.94%	40.13%	19.93%

	Corner	0%	34.12%	39.58%	26.3%
FOV=45°	Central	89.93%	0.34%	6.74%	2.99%
	Side	70.02%	11.08%	12.07%	6.83%
	Corner	0%	32.86%	41.89%	25.24%
FOV=60°	Central	82.51%	4.74%	8.25%	4.5%
	Side	59.32%	16.92%	16.05%	7.72%
	Corner	49.44%	17.51%	20.07%	12.97%
FOV=85°	Central	75.7%	9.04%	9.73%	5.53%
	Side	50.9%	22.4%	16.9%	9.8%
	Corner	40.7%	23.3%	21.5%	14.4%

The impulse responses of the receiver with FOV=30° have been plotted in Figure 3-9(a). When it is placed at the center of the room, the LoS component first arrives at the detector around 10ns. There is no one reflection component because the FOV of the detector is so small that the photon cannot arrive via only one reflection path. The two and the three reflection components can be detected but power ratios of them are very small. The cases of placing the receiver at the side and at the corner of the room are similar. The reflection components can arrive at almost the same time, 14ns (side) and 16ns (corner). But the one reflection component dominates at the arrival time. LoS component does not appear because of the small FOV.

If the receiver with FOV=45° is employed, the impulse response is quite similar to the previous case at central position. But the one reflection component can be detected although the power ratio is much less than other components. If the receiver is placed at the side of the room, the LoS component and the one reflection component simultaneously arrive at the detector around 13ns. If the receiver is placed at the corner, the receiver can only detect the reflection components starting from 16ns.

If the FOV of the detector is enlarged to 60°, the impulse response has two peaks, which are the LoS and the one reflection components, appearing at 10ns and 20ns respectively. For the cases of side position and corner position, the impulse responses happen at 13ns and 16ns. The most optical power is concentrated in the LoS component.

The receiver with FOV=85° must be taken into account because it is widely adopted in many theoretical simulations and practical experiments. The impulse responses at different positions are similar to the cases of the receiver with FOV=60°. In Table 3-4, the ratio of impulse power of LoS component among the whole impulse power is less than that in the case of FOV=60°. Many higher order reflection components can be captured by a receiver with larger FOV, but they reduce the impulse power ratio of LoS component.

3.3.3.2 Frequency response

Figure 3-10: Frequency responses of channel characteristic at the center, side, corner positions with different field of view (FOV)

Table 3-6: 3 dB channel bandwidth (MHz)

	Central	Side	Corner
FOV=30°	ideal	16	20
FOV=45°	ideal	500	19
FOV=60°	ideal	500	500
FOV=85°	ideal	500	376

The frequency responses of the receiver with different FOVs at different positions have been presented from Figure 3-10. Generally, 3 dB channel bandwidth is an important benchmark to quantify the range of low pass characteristic. At the central position, the 3 dB channel bandwidth are almost ideal in all FOV cases because the receiver can always capture sufficient LoS component. At the side position, the 3dB channel bandwidth decreases to only 16MHz for the receiver with FOV=30° because there is no contribution of LoS component and the impulse power ration of 3 bounces reflection increases up to 19.93%. For the other FOV cases, although they all achieve 500MHz bandwidth, the magnitude responses decrease along with the increase of the frequency. From the side position to the corner position, the 3dB channel bandwidth decreases from 500 MHz to 19MHz due to the lack of LoS component and the increase of higher order reflection for the receiver with FOV=45°. Note that the 3dB channel bandwidth of FOV=85° is smaller than that of FOV=60°. The reason is that the higher order reflections captured by larger FOV receiver decrease the bandwidth of the channel. The higher order

reflections have significant impact only at low frequencies; the high-frequency magnitude response is characterized by the first-order reflection only [48].

3.3.3.3 RMS delay spread

Figure 3-11: RMS delay spread of the receiver with different field of view (FOV)

Table 3-7: RMS delay spread (ns)

	Dynamic Range	Average
FOV=30°	0.142~9.665	5.047
FOV=45°	0.253~9.171	0.906
FOV=60°	0.382~1.203	0.608
FOV=85°	0.530~1.525	0.810

In Figure 3-11, the three-dimensional (3D) profiles of RMS delay spread have been plotted. Here we only focus on the dynamic range of RMS delay spread is from 0 to 1.5ns. In the case of the receiver with FOV=30°, short time delay is limited in a round area directly below the transmitter. Although the average time delay of the receiver with FOV=45° is 0.906ns, the largest delay is measured up to 9.171ns at the corner of the room. When FOV is enlarged to 60°, the maximum delay spread is dramatically reduced to 1.203ns. However, if the receiver with FOV=85° is employed, the maximum, minimum and average values increase compared to the previous case. As the FOV increases, the receiver can capture many higher order reflection components that reduce the contribution of LoS component.

3.3.3.4 Optical path loss

Figure 3-12: Optical path loss of the receiver with different field of view (FOV)

Table 3-8: Optical path loss (dB)

	Dynamic Range	Average
FOV=30°	-131.2697~-151.0737	-139.9566
FOV=45°	-131.0577~-147.6663	-134.1618
FOV=60°	-130.6796~-138.1998	-133.1760
FOV=85°	-130.3037~-137.7946	-132.6282

The simulation results of optical path loss have been listed in Table 3-8. As the FOV is enlarged, the received optical power increase.

3.4 VLC devices

3.4.1 LED Source

3.4.1.1 Phosphor Converted(PC)-LED

The method of coating LEDs of one color with phosphors of different colors is nominated as phosphor converted (PC)-LED. The structure of PC-LED is presented in Figure 3-13. In the industry, white LEDs is commonly manufactured by coating blue LEDs made of Indium Gallium Nitride (InGaN) with a yellow phosphor material containing Cerium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Ce^{3+} YAG). The InGaN LEDs directly emit blue light whose peak is in the range between 450nm and 470nm. The yellow phosphor converts a fraction of blue light to green, yellow and red portion of the spectrum, which is roughly between 500nm and 700nm. The other blue light is leaked out. The mixture light produced by PC-LED can be categorized as warm-white, neutral-white or cool-white depending on the amount of phosphor. Moreover, coating with several phosphor layers of distinct colors, the emitted spectrum can be broadened. Due to the simplicity of manufacturing, the phosphor-conversion method is the most popular way for making commercial white LEDs in the current market.

Figure 3-13: PC-LED structure

3.4.1.2 RGB-LED

In physics, it is a common knowledge that white light is mixed by different color lights. Hence, people use three monochromatic light LED chips emitting red, green and blue (RGB) light to produce white light. This method is called RGB LEDs. However, RGB LEDs are seldom used as illumination device because it requires complicated electric circuit to control the blending and diffusion of different colors. A color rendering index (CRI) is a quantitative measure of the ability of a light source to reveal the colors of various objects faithfully in comparison with an ideal or natural light source. Generally, a light source is defined as an illumination device when its CRI is larger than 90. Because LEDs are temperature-sensitive unit, the emitted color light could be influenced by the temperature. In the decade, RGB LEDs have been adopted to simultaneously transmit different signals having Gigabit transmission speed. Nevertheless, it is difficult to be employed in many practical applications due to the low CRI and manufacture complexity.

Figure 3-14: RGB LED structure

3.4.1.3 Organic LED (OLED)

Organic LED (OLED) is a flat light emitting technology, made by placing the electroluminescent material comprising the emissive layer between positive and negative carriers. The organic material emits light when electrical current is applied. The organic materials can be small organic molecules or polymers. OLED has been used in various panel displays because it has lots of advantages over LCD displays, such as better contrast, higher brightness, much faster refresh rate, lower power consumption. Due to the simple design, OLED can be used to create flexible and transparent displays. However, OLED is not suitable for high speed applications because its typical frequency response is in the order of 100's of kHz. Researchers are working on improving the frequency response by equalization.

Figure 3-15: OLED

3.4.1.4 Micro LED (μ LED)

Micro LED is actually a LED array consisting of many microscopic LEDs whose size ranges from 14 μm to 84 μm . Due to the tiny size of each unit, micro LED is sometimes referred to μ LED. It is suitable to be used as display because of better contrast, response time and energy efficiency. Compared to OLED, μ LED not only offers higher brightness and higher efficiency, but also longer lifetime. Moreover, μ LED has been explored as a light source for visible light communication with the speeds up to 1.5 Gb/s [49][50][51][52][53]. The electro-optics response is in the order of nanosecond, and the 3dB bandwidth reaches hundreds of MHz due to the low capacitance in the LEDs. The light spectrum of μ LED is typically in the range of 370-520 nm. Using the polymer based color conversion, the emitted light (blue) can be converted to red and green, finally mixed to produce white light. P. Manousiadis *et al.* in [54] used this scheme to test the communication ability of GaN- μ LED, and obtained the aggregated data rate of 2.3 Gb/s.

Figure 3-16: μ LED structure

3.4.1.5 Comparison of LED Sources

In order to select a suitable transmitter that is probably used in the corresponding VLC application, we briefly list the difference of each type of LEDs in Table 3-9. 3dB bandwidth represent the transmission capacity, so μ LEDs should be the best choice for high speed scenarios. However, several drawbacks, such as low efficacy, high cost and high complexity, largely limits usage of μ LEDs. RGB LEDs have the second largest bandwidth and they have been experimented to achieve the highest data rate [55], but they require an additional circuit to precisely control the ratio among red, green, and blue light. PC-LEDs is the simplest way to provide illumination as well as communication, but their transmission speed is severely limited by the small bandwidth caused by slow response of yellow phosphor. Due to small bandwidth and low efficacy, OLEDs are suitable for display and offer low speed optical wireless services.

Table 3-9: Comparison of different types of LEDs

Parameter	PC-LED	RGB LED	μ LED	OLED
Bandwidth	3-5MHz	10-20MHz	>300MHz	<1MHz
Efficacy	130lm/W	65lm/W	N/A	45lm/W
Cost	Low	High	High	Lowest
Complexity	Low	Moderate	Highest	High
Application	Illumination		Bio-sensors	Display

3.4.2 Photodiode

As the information is modulated onto light carriers, a photodiode that precisely converts optical intensity into electrical current is the most important device in the whole VLC systems. Photodiodes are usually designed to operate in reverse bias. When the P-N junction in the semiconductor is illuminated by light, a photocurrent is produced. This mechanism is also known as inner photoelectric effect. When a photodiode is used in a visible light communication system, several critical performance parameters ought to be considered.

Spectral response range: The photocurrent produced by a given level of incident light varies with the wavelength.

Photosensitivity: It is the relation between the photoelectric sensitivity and the wavelength.

Terminal capacitance: An effective capacitor is formed at the PN junction of a photodiode. Its capacitance is termed the junction capacitance and is one of parameters that determine the bandwidth available for signal modulation and thus data transmission.

Dark current: The current through the photodiode in the absence of light is called dark current. It actually is a noise

source inside the device.

Noise-equivalent power (NEP): The NEP is the amount of light equivalent to the noise level of a device. NEP is essentially the minimum detectable power.

This section introduces two photodiodes: PIN photodiode and Avalanche photodiode, which are commonly used in the VLC systems.

3.4.2.1 PIN

PIN photodiodes use PIN junction rather than PN junction to increase the speed of response. There are three regions in this type of diode. There is a P-region, an intrinsic region, and an N-region. The P-region and N-region are comparatively heavily doped than the P-region and N-region of usual P-N diodes. The width of the intrinsic region should be larger than the space charge width of a normal PN junction. The PIN photodiode operates with an applied reverse bias voltage and when the reverse bias is applied, the space charge region must cover the intrinsic region completely. Electron hole pairs are generated in the space charge region by photon absorption. The switching speed of frequency response of photo diode is inversely proportional to the life time. The switching speed can be enhanced by a small minority carrier lifetime. For the photo detector applications where the speed of response is important, the depletion region width should be made as large as possible for small minority carrier lifetime as a result the switch speed also increases. The diagram of a normal PIN photodiode is given below.

Figure 3-17: Structure of PIN photodiode

3.4.2.2 APD

The APD (avalanche photodiode) is a high sensitivity photodiode that are used to detect extremely weak light intensities. The structure of APD is presented in Figure 3-18. The APD possesses a similar structure to that of the PN or PIN photodiode. The main difference of the avalanche photodiode to other forms of photodiode is that it operates under a high reverse bias condition. This enables avalanche multiplication of the holes and electrons created by the photon / light impact. As a photon enters the depletion region and creates a hole-electron pair, these charge carriers will be pulled by the very high electric field away from one another. Their velocity will increase to such an extent that when they collide with the lattice, they will create further hole-electron pairs and the process will repeat. The avalanche action enables the gain of the diode to be increased many times, providing a very much greater level of sensitivity. Avalanche diodes are usually employed in the case of very low optical signal strengths, but are also used for applications with high modulation frequencies.

Figure 3-18: Structure of APD

3.5 Key technologies

3.5.1 Modulation

This section briefly introduces some modulation schemes that have been applied into VLC communication systems.

3.5.1.1 OOK

OOK is the simplest modulation scheme for VLC. The signals modulated by OOK have two statuses where “on” means high voltage and “off” means low voltage. While the modulation is logically OOK, OOK “off” does not necessarily mean the light is completely turned off; rather, the intensity of the light may simply be reduced as long as one can distinguish clearly between the “on” and “off” levels. Using a simple first-order analogue equalizer, H. Le Minh et al. achieved a data rate of 100Mb/s with OOK NRZ modulation in 2009 [56]. In the same year, 125Mb/s over 5 meters using OOK [57] were presented by J. Vucic et al. Note that PINs were used to detect optical signals. In 2010, the data rate of OOK based system reached 230Mb/s due to the employed APD [58].

3.5.1.2 PPM

In PPM, the symbol duration is divided into n slots of equal duration, and a single pulse is transmitted in one of the n slots. The position of the pulse identifies the transmitted information symbol. The average power requirement for PPM is lower than OOK [59] since it avoids the DC and lower frequency component of the spectrum [16], but it is less bandwidth efficient [60][61][62]. System complexity is increased on PPM compared with OOK, as it requires stricter bit and symbol synchronization at the receiver [63][64]. IEEE 802.15.7 standard [65] specifies a pulse modulation scheme called Variable PPM (VPPM) which is a hybrid of PPM and pulse width modulation (PWM). In VPPM, the bits are encoded by choosing different position of pulse as in PPM; however, the width of the pulse can also be modified as needed. VPPM retains the simplicity and robustness of PPM while allowing different dimming levels by altering the pulse width. A limitation of VPPM-based dimming support is its low spectral efficiency. Multi-pulse position modulation (MPPM) [66] is a natural

extension of single-pulse PPM by using two or more pulses to convey information in each symbol duration. This can be accomplished by placing more than one pulse in all possible ways among the n slots, generating a much larger number of usable information symbols when n is large. Hence, MPPM can achieve a higher spectral efficiency compared to PPM. MPPM is also robust to the LED nonlinearity due to its binary power amplitude. Since the number of pulses is identical in all MPPM symbols and hence the light intensity remains constant, MPPM can naturally be regarded as a flickering-mitigation modulation. MPPM is an attractive modulation scheme with dimming support for low-rate VLC applications.

3.5.1.3 PAM

PAM is a bandwidth efficient modulation scheme where the message information is modulated into the amplitude of a series of signal pulse. Modulation schemes employing multiple intensity levels such as PAM may undergo nonlinearity in LEDs luminous efficacy. Due to the dependence of the color of LED emission on input current and temperature, multiple symbol levels of PAM are subject to shifts in color temperature due to variation in drive current [67].

3.5.1.4 CSK

Due to the use of multi-color LEDs in VLC, CSK acting as a special modulation scheme has been introduced in the IEEE 802.15.7 standards [68]. The scheme does not use the varying current to drive the multi-color LEDs, but transmit the white light consisting of multiple wavelengths. The CSK symbols are drawn from the CIE 1931 coordinates shown in Fig. 5-1 (a). There are seven possible wavelength bands can be chosen to provide support for multiple LED color for communication. The CSK signal is generated by using three color light sources out of the seven color bands. The picked wavelength bands determine the vertices of a triangle inside which the constellation points (corresponding to CIE coordinates) of the CSK symbols lie. Figure 3-19 (b) shows that only valid color band combinations generate a triangle. The color point for each symbol is generated by modulating the intensity of RGB chips. 4 CSK, 8CSK, and 16CSK constellations are presented in Figure 3-20 where the absolute values of each symbol point are defined in [68]. However, implementation of CSK requires a complex circuit structure. An optional feedback loop from the receiver can be implemented for color calibration and avoiding interference from other light sources [69].

Figure 3-19: (a) CIE 1931 xy color coordinate

(b) Valid CSK constellation example for codes (110, 010, 000)

Figure 3-20: 4CSK , 8CSK , 16CSK constellations

3.5.1.5 OFDM

Orthogonal frequency multiplexing access (OFDM) has been extensively used in radio frequency communications because it is an effective technique to combat the inter-symbol interference (ISI) caused by multipath propagation. In the decades, the application of optical OFDM has been studied, and it can support high speed optical wireless transmission service, especially in an indoor environment. Intensity modulation and direct detection (IM/DD) is usually applied into optical wireless systems due to its simple implementation. However, only real and non-negative value can be used to modulate the intensity of optical signal. The OFDM symbols in the frequency domain have to be constraint to Hermitian symmetry to ensure real but bipolar optical signals in the time domain. In order to obtain non-negative signals, lots of modulation schemes have been proposed, and they can be divided into two categories, which are DC biased optical (DCO)-OFDM [70] and clipped optical OFDM. DCO-OFDM is not an optical power efficient scheme because adding a DC bias consumes large energy of transmitting a DCO-OFDM signal. Asymmetrically clipped optical (ACO)-OFDM [71] signals are generated by clipping all the negative samples rather than adding a DC bias, thus ACO-OFDM is much more power efficient than DCO-OFDM. However, the spectral efficiency is reduced by half since symbols are only mapped onto the odd subcarriers. Based on ACO-OFDM, many techniques have been proposed to modulate the even subcarriers. Flip-OFDM (U-OFDM) [72][73] modulates all the subcarriers instead of only even subcarriers. The positive samples are transmitted in one OFDM symbol period and the negative samples are transmitted in the subsequent symbol period. In Asymmetrically clipped DC biased (ADO)-OFDM [74], the even subcarriers are modulated by DCO-OFDM. Although the spectral efficiency as high as DCO-OFDM, the DC bias results in a large power consumption. Hybrid ACO (HACO)-OFDM [75] modulates PAM symbols on the even subcarriers, but a PAM is less energy efficient than an equal order QAM. Asymmetrically and symmetrically clipped optical (ASCO)-OFDM [76] applied clipping approach into the signals transformed from even subcarriers. The clipped signals on the even subcarriers are called symmetrically clipped optical (SCO)-OFDM. The positive samples only contains half of the information, so the negative samples have to be transmitted in the consecutive time slot. It is considered as a combination of ACO-OFDM and U-OFDM. Spectral and Energy Efficient (SEE)-OFDM [77] transmits several superposed clipped signals which are converted by different length of IFFT/FFT. Enhanced Unipolar (eU)-OFDM [78] is quite similar to SEE-OFDM and achieves the same spectral efficiency when superposing the same number of signals within one OFDM symbol period.

3.5.1.6 Carrierless Amplitude and Phase modulation (CAP)

CAP modulation is the variant of QAM scheme used in single carrier systems. It is an alternative to OFDM that can increase the VLC link capacity under limited bandwidth. Instead of modulating the amplitude of two orthogonal carriers, CAP signals are generated by combining two PAM signals filtered through In-phase and quadrature filter, whose impulse response forms a Hilbert transform pair. Thus, the two transformed PAM signals are orthogonal to each other [79]. A DC bias is then added to make the signal unipolar. At the receiver, the inverse Hilbert filters, followed by a Decision Feedback Equalizer (DFE) is utilized to extract the information. The orthogonality of two signals is achieved by Hilbert transformation, which is simpler than FFT or IFFT in terms of implementation complexity. Obviously, CAP signals have much lower PAPR. However, CAP is not immune to frequency selective fading, thereby causing to degrade the system performance. OFDM can utilize power loading and bit loading to map the proper modulation orders to each subcarrier, making CAP less flexible than OFDM [80][81].

3.5.2 Equalization

Despite having huge spectrum, VLC still face the challenge of limited bandwidth. The modulated bandwidth depends on the minimum 3dB bandwidth of LEDs, channel characteristic, and photo detector. The characteristic of channel model has been introduced in Section 3.3, and optical channel has large available bandwidth when transceivers are placed at proper position. Commercial photo detectors, such as PD or APD, usually have 3dB bandwidth in the order of tens of MHz. More severely, commercial PC-LEDs only have a 3dB bandwidth of around 2.5MHz [82]. There are lots of methods which can be adapted to counter the bandwidth limitation of the LEDs and the VLC system.

Blue filter: Coating Yellow phosphor on the blue LED makes the PC-LED cheap and simple for manufacture, but it results in the limited modulation bandwidth. The blue light driven by LED current fluctuating with modulated signals illuminate on the yellow phosphor to produce white light. But the yellow phosphor cannot response to the modulated signal at high frequencies, hence reducing the data rate. Blue filter can enhance the modulation bandwidth when employed. Only blue light can transmit through the blue filter, so the overall optical power arriving at the detection area is much smaller than that of emitted white light.

Post-equalization: The experiment of [12] shows that the bandwidth of white light (Luxeon STAR) LED is only 2.5MHz and the blue response is approximately 14MHz. The data links are 5 Mb/s and 40 Mb/s for white light and blue light respectively. Using a blue filter in combination with a RC first-order equalizer can extend the bandwidth to 50MHz, which is 25 times wider than un-equalized LED bandwidth. A higher data rate at 100Mb/s (OOK-NRZ) is achieved. A post-equalizer consisting of RC component and a broadband operational amplifier (OPA847) [83] can further extend the bandwidth to 151MHz where the original 3dB bandwidth of white light and blue light are 3MHz and 12MHz respectively. The transmission data rate of 340Mb/s is achieved below the BER of 2×10^{-3} .

Pre-equalization: Demonstration in [84] using a multiple resonant driving circuit to extend the bandwidth at the transmitter. Each LED is added with a capacitor having a different resonant frequency. A group of resonant circuit increase the modulation bandwidth to 25 MHz compared with 2.5 MHz. A hardware pre-equalization circuit having constant-resistance symmetrical bridged-T structure is reported to further extend the bandwidth [85]. Its cascaded version with assist of blue filter, the bandwidth of VLC system is increased from 17 MHz to 366 MHz [86].

Subcarrier equalization: The modulation bandwidth can be extended by various hardware equalizers, but it is hard to obtain further extension due to the limitation of devices or chips. In order to achieve higher data rate, subcarrier equalization

is an effective approach for VLC OFDM systems. The achievable data rate can be maximized based on the Electrical-Optical-Electrical (EOE) channel characteristics of each subcarrier, which determines the power and constellation size used. So it is known as power loading and bit loading respectively. Using the bit and power loading algorithm, the data rate of the pre-equalization system [87] is greatly increased to 2 Gb/s.

3.5.3 Coding

Channel coding is a technique used for controlling errors in data transmission over unreliable or noisy channels. The key idea is that the transmitter encodes the message in a redundant way by using an error-correcting code. Some conventional coding, such as Reed Solomon (RS) code, convolutional code, Turbo code, and low density parity check (LDPC) are quite popular in the radio frequency communications. Since modulation and coding can be operated in the electrical domain, these codes have been proposed in the standardization of IEEE 802.15.7 Short-Range Optical Wireless Communication. PHY I adopts OOK and VPPM to realize low data rate outdoor applications. A concatenated code of convolutional code and RS code are developed to overcome the pass loss due to long distance transmission and interference caused by ambient noises. The RS encoder output is padded with zeros to form an interleaver boundary. The padded zeros are then punctured (discarded) and the result is sent to the inner convolutional encoder. PHY II was designed to transmit higher data rate in the indoor scenario where the coding requirements are less stringent for short distances. Only RS code is used to correct errors and increase the system reliability. The channel coding for PHY III is RS (64, 32) code. Compared to advanced coding schemes such as LDPC, RS and convolutional codes are preferred in the cases of short data frames, hard decision decoding, low complexity, and their ability to interface well with RLL line codes. More PHY layers have been proposed in the latest version of IEEE 802.15.7r1 in 2017. PHY VII is designed to use some high efficient modulation schemes, such as OFDM and SC-FDMA, on the low-bandwidth resources. A convolutional encoder of coding rate 1/2, 2/3, or 3/4 is utilized for the desired data rate.

For PHY VIII high-bandwidth PHY, the LDPC code may be selected between two information block sizes of 4320 or 920 bits and 5 code rates of 1/2, 2/3, 5/6, 16/18 or 20/21 [88].

3.5.4 Dimming Control

Dimming control has been considered as a key feature of VLC to save energy and facilitate intelligent lighting solutions. It will be desirable to maintain communication when the light source is dimmed over a large range. Since LEDs are driven by current, the brightness of an LED can be adjusted by the average amount of drive current. Hence, it can be categorized into analog dimming, called Continuous Current Reduction (CCR). It is simple to be implemented in the VLC systems with PC-LED or RGB-LED. But the wavelength of photons emitted changes with drive current, causing chromaticity shifts [89][90], thereby affecting the efficiency of communication and illumination. Compared to analog dimming, digital dimming is to maintain the average duty cycle or signal density in a specified time period. It is preferred to use digital dimming for precisely control rather than analog dimming. Some dimming methods for different modulation scheme are introduced in this section.

Variable OOK (VOOK): In OOK scheme, 1 bit is represented by a rectangle pulse with amplitude $2P$ in the symbol period T while 0 bit by no pulse. Thus, the signal can be written by, $x(t) = 2Pd \cdot \text{rect}(t/T)$, where d is the information bit $d \in \{0,1\}$. Dimming is achieved by adjusting the duty cycle δ_d of an OOK pulse. $\delta_d = \tau_d / T$, where τ_d is the

duration of information bit.

Variable PPM (VPPM): Information bit is represented by position in a pulse, and dimming method of VPPM is realized by transmitting symbols with different pulse width. So it is a combination of PPM and PWM. The duty cycle is proportional to the pulse duration time within a symbol, and it is equal to dimming level δ_d . In order to compare these two-dimming scheme, we list the symbols of VOOK and VPPM in Table 3-10.

Table 3-10: Symbols of VOOK and VPPM

γ	VOOK		VPPM		
	δ_d	codeword	δ_d	Codeword(Bit 0)	Codeword(Bit 1)
1.0	0.0	1111111111	1.0	1111111111	1111111111
0.9	0.2	dd11111111	0.9	1111111110	0111111111
0.8	0.4	dddd111111	0.8	1111111100	0011111111
0.7	0.6	dddddd1111	0.7	1111111000	0001111111
0.6	0.8	ddddddd11	0.6	1111110000	0000111111
0.5	1.0	dddddddddd	0.5	1111100000	0000011111
0.4	0.8	ddddddd00	0.4	1111000000	0000001111
0.3	0.6	dddddd0000	0.3	1110000000	0000000111
0.2	0.4	ddd0000000	0.2	1100000000	0000000011
0.1	0.2	dd00000000	0.1	1000000000	0000000001
0.0	0.0	0000000000	0.0	0000000000	0000000000

CSK: The use of multi-color LEDs makes CSK available in practical system, so it was specified in IEEE 802.15.7 standard. The total power of lighting device that consists of multi-color LEDs must be constant although each light source may have a different instantaneous output power. CSK dimming is achieved by adjusting the amplitude of driving current of each LED. It is indeed a challenge to maintain the requisite intensity of the center color of the color constellation when changing the current of all the LEDs at the same time. Although there is no flicker issue associated with CSK due to amplitude variations, care needs to be observed during CSK dimming to avoid unexpected color shift in the light source.

PWM-DMT [91]: PWM also has been investigated in the application of Discrete Multi-Tone (DMT). The DMT waveform are actually sampled by PWM signals with different pulse width. Fig. 5-3 (a) shows the normalized PWM signals at two dimming levels of 80% and 20%. Fig. 5-3 (b) presents the PWM-sampled DMT signals for the same dimming levels. In the operation of dimming DMT signals with PWM, two practical problems should be illustrated. In one hand, The PWM frequencies must be at least twice the highest subcarrier to avoid subcarrier interference. In another hand, the bandwidth of PMT-sampled signal cannot exceed the 3dB bandwidth of LED, otherwise causing performance degradation. So this dimming method will reduce the modulation bandwidth of DMT by half.

Figure 3-21: (a) Normalized PWM waveform, indication of the PWM period (T_{PWM}), and the on time of the LED (T_1). Both for 80% and 20% dimming. (b) PWM-sampled DMT signal for the same settings.

RPO-OFDM [92]: Another mixture of multi-carrier modulation and PWM is called reverse polarity OFDM (RPO-OFDM). RPO-OFDM signals are given by

$$i_{LED}(t) = \begin{cases} i_{PWM}(t) - m \times i_{OFDM}(t), & 0 \leq t \leq T \\ i_{PWM}(t) + m \times i_{OFDM}(t), & T < t \leq T_{PWM} \end{cases} \quad (3-11)$$

where m is a real valued scaling factor of OFDM modulating signal. Without adding DC bias, the average power of ACO-OFDM signal is too small to drive the LED. Elgala *et al.* makes ACO-OFDM transmit on a series of PWM pulse. A part of ACO-OFDM signal is subtracted by high voltage of PWM pulse, and the rest is added by low voltage. The duty cycle of PWM can be recognized as dimming level of RPO-OFDM. This simple combination algorithm is able to achieve high data rate as well as a large dimming range. This scheme has been implemented in practical system shown in [93]. Note that the requirement of dimming control is to establish a connection between dimming level and data rate. However, the achievement of RPO-OFDM dimming scheme does not satisfy the requirement because the PWM period is always fully loaded. Thus, more dimming solutions are encouraged to be proposed in the future.

Figure 3-22: Optical RPO-OFDM signal waveform based on ACO-OFDM at 70% dimming level (upper) and 20% dimming level (lower)

3.5.5 Multiplexing

Visible light communications has an inherent property of multiplexing since white light can be generated by red, green, and blue light. Although RGB-LEDs have not been used as commercial illumination device due to its higher cost, they have some advantages over phosphor-covered LEDs, such as larger bandwidth and independent channel. Thus, VLC systems using RGB-LEDs as transmitters have the potential for wavelength division multiplexing (WDM). Three chips can be modulated by the different signals because different light signals are transmitted through their own optical spectrum, which are independent channels with no correlation. Hence they can be filtered out by using the corresponding optical filters. Parallel transmission can linearly enhance the capacity gain with the number of independent channels. The transceiver configuration of utilizing different light spectrum is considered as VLC MIMO system, which greatly increase the data rate.

The first demonstration of WDM capacity was experimented in the OFDM base system using RGB LEDs in 2011 [94]. The achievable data rate is 803Mb/s over 0.12 meters. G. Cossu, R. Corsini, E. Ciaramella *et al.* adopted the transceiver configuration of RGB LEDs and APD. The performances of OFDM based VLC system were reported from 780Mb/s over 2.5 meters to 3.4 Gb/s over 0.3 meters [95][96][97]. Moreover, downlink and uplink can be easily separated with the assist of WDM. An asynchronous bi-directional VLC system was presented in [98] where a 575Mb/s downlink was transmitted by red and green LEDs, a 300Mb/s uplink was transmitted by a single blue LED. Besides red, green and blue, the yellow light was added by N. Chi *et al.* to improve the aggregate data rate. Hence, a RGBY LED based system with high order CAP and post-equalization burst the speed up to 8 Gb/s [99].

4. Conclusion

With the deep investigation of high frequency channel properties, the development of high frequency devices and the research on resolutions to resolve the issues encountered when utilizing higher frequency bands in practical wireless communication systems, now it is verified not only feasible but necessary to consider the exploitation of high frequency bands, i.e., mmWave bands for the upcoming 5G systems and for future wireless systems. For mmWave, recent research activities focus on resolving issues to enable the usage of mmWave bands for the 5G deployment around 2020. Those research efforts include the discussion of feasible spectrum resources suitable for the 5G system; further investigation of the radio propagation properties by channel measurement and channel modeling to identify the real issues to be solved before successful deployment; identification of suitable deployment scenarios; considerations of the impact of those channel characteristics on system design; and candidate key technologies to resolve practical problems. This paper present and summarize the recent progress of mmWave related research from all above-mentioned angles. Based on the review and summary of the research status, people are more confident on the practical deployment of mmWave bands for 5G systems. On the other hand, people never stop to look at the opportunities to exploit additional spectrum resources. To give a report on such activities, this paper reviews the status of the research on visible light communications. A thorough review and analysis of different aspects related to that research direction is provided. More specifically, it contains the analysis of spectrum availability, considerations on deployment scenario, introduction of characteristics of channels and devices and some key technologies. We believe such research work may lead to commercialization of visible light communications in the future.

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Glossary

3G	3rd generation mobile networks
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	4th generation mobile networks
5G	5th generation mobile networks
μ LED	Micro light-emitting diode
ACO-OFDM	Asymmetrically clipped optical-OFDM
ADO-OFDM	Asymmetrically clipped DC biased optical-OFDM
AoA	(Azimuth) Angle of arrival
APD	Avalanche photodiode
ARAS	Azimuth root mean square angle spread
ASCO-OFDM	Asymmetrically and symmetrically clipped optical-OFDM

ASU	Antenna switch unit
AWGN	Additive white Gaussian noise
BA2BA	Biconical antenna to biconical antenna
BS	Base station
BUPT	Beijing University of Posts & Telecommunications
CAP	Carrierless amplitude and phase modulation
CCR	Continuous current reduction
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
CDL	Clustered delay line
Ce ³⁺ YAG	Cerium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet
CIR	Channel impulse response
CMCC	China Mobile Communications Corporation
CoMP	Coordinated multipoint
CRI	Color rendering index
CSI	Channel state information
CSK	Color shift keying
DC	Direct current
DCI	Downlink control information
DCO-OFDM	DC biased optical-OFDM
DFE	Decision feedback equalizer
DL	Downlink
DMT	Discrete multi-tone
DS	Delay spread
DVD	Digital video disk
EESS	Earth exploration satellite service
EIRP	Equivalent isotropic radiated power
EMI	Electromagnetic interference
EOE	Electrical-optical-electrical
eMBB	Enhanced mobile broadband.

EoA	Elevation angle of arrival
ERAS	Elevation root mean square angle spread
eU-OFDM	Enhanced unipolar-OFDM
FDD	Frequency-division duplex
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
FoV	Field of view
FSS	Fixed satellite service
GSCM	Geometry based stochastic channel model
HA2HA	Horn antenna to horn antenna
HACO-OFDM	Hybrid ACO-OFDM
HB	Hybrid beamforming
HBS	Human body shadowing
HF	High frequency
HPBW	Half-power beam width
IFFT	Inverse fast Fourier transform
IMT	International Mobile Telecommunications
InGaN	Indium gallium nitride
ISD	Inter-site distance
ISS	Interim satellite service
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-R	ITU-Radiocommunication Sector
KF	Rician K-factor
LDPC	Low density parity check
LED	Light-emitting diode
LF	Low frequency
Li-Fi	Visible light communication
LoS	Line of sight
LTE	Long Time Evolution
MAC-CE	Medium access control-control element

MIIT	Ministry of Industry and Information Technology of China
MIMO	Multiple-input and multiple-output
MMSE	Minimum mean square error
mMTC	Massive machine type communications
mmWave	Millimeter wave
MPC	Multi-path component
MPPM	Multi-pulse-position modulation
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
MS	Mobile station
MU-MIMO	Multi-use multiple-input and multiple-output
NEP	Noise-equivalent power
NLoS	Non-line of sight
NR	New radio
OFDM	Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing
OLED	Organic light-emitting diode
OMP	Orthogonal matching pursuit
OOK	On-off keying
OPL	Optical path-loss
OWC	Optical wireless communications
PA	Power amplifier
PAM	Pulse-amplitude modulation
PAS	Power angle spectrum
PC-LED	Phosphor converted light-emitting diode
PDF	Probability density function
PN	Pseudo-noise
PPM	Pulse-position modulation
PWM	Pulse-width modulation
QAM	Quadrature amplitude modulation
QCL	Quasi-co-located

RAS	Root mean square angle spread
RAT	Radio access technology
RDS	Root mean square delay spread
RF	Radio frequency
RGB	Red, green, and blue
RMS	Root mean square
RMSE	Root mean square error
RNS	Radio navigation service
RPO-OFDM	Reverse polarity-OFDM
RRC	Radio resource control
RS	Reference signal
RS code	Reed-Solomon code
RSRP	Reference signal receiving power
RX	Receiver
SAGE	Space-alternating generalized expectation-maximization
SC-FDMA	Single carrier-frequency division multiple access
SCO-OFDM	Symmetrically clipped optical-OFDM
SEE-OFDM	Spectrum and energy efficient-OFDM
SF	Shadowing fading
SIMO	Single-input and multi-output
SINR	Signal-to-interference-and-noise ratio
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
TA	Timing advance
TDD	Time-division duplex
TDL	Tapped delay line
TRP	Transmission reception point
TX	Transmitter
UAN	Ultra-dense network aggregation node
UCNC	User-centric no-cell network

UDN	Ultra-dense network
UE	User equipment
UL	Uplink
URLLC	Ultra-reliable low latency Communication
UMi	Urban micro cell
V2X	Vehicle to X communication
VLC	Visible light communication
VOOK	Variable on-off keying
VPPM	Variable pulse-position modulation
WDM	Wavelength division multiplexing
Wi-Fi	Wireless local area network
WRC	World Radiocommunication Conference
XPR	Cross-polarization power ratio
ZoA	Zenith angle of arrival

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Contributors:

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